

Original Paper

An Internal-Clock Route to the Hydrogenic Energy Ladder

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Abstract: De Broglie's matter-wave picture begins with a relativistic internal periodicity attached to the particle and an associated phase wave that, for particle speed v , has group velocity v but phase velocity c^2/v . Later wave and semiclassical treatments make this associated wave phase the object whose global consistency quantizes bound motion. This paper keeps the internal-clock starting point and the loop-closure idea, but asks whether the Coulomb action ladder can be obtained before postulating a matter wave. We assume that a field-dressed charge supports a long-lived localized clock line whose phase advances with proper time. In the nucleus frame, removing the main laboratory clock frequency leaves a slow envelope phase. For nonrelativistic bound Coulomb motion this proper-time lag is proportional to the mechanical action accumulated around the independent radial and angular returns. Requiring the slow clock phase to close on those returns, after the standard radial turning-point and Coulomb-origin half-shifts, selects the usual Coulomb action lattice. Substitution into the Coulomb Hamiltonian gives the hydrogenic energy law $E_n \propto -1/n^2$, with the clock action scale calibrated by $J_{\tau_0} = \hbar$. The result is conditional: the finite-size field-dressed electron, the long-lived clock line, the standard half-shifts, and the calibration of J_{τ_0} are inputs. The paper does not claim to derive the value of \hbar , full wave functions, full radiative stability of the atom, fine structure, Lamb shifts, or quantum measurement statistics. Its purpose is limited: to show, with all inputs visible, how the hydrogenic $1/n^2$ ladder follows from proper-time closure of an internal clock.

Keywords: Hydrogen atom; Coulomb problem; internal clock; proper time; semiclassical action; EBK quantization; Maxwell–Lorentz electrodynamics; quantum foundations

1. Introduction: an internal-clock route to the hydrogenic ladder

Hydrogen has a simple energy ladder,

$$E_n \propto -\frac{1}{n^2},$$

but the usual derivations introduce that ladder through a wave phase. In the Schrödinger treatment the wavefunction must be regular and single-valued. In semiclassical action quantization, the phase accumulated around closed orbital loops must return to itself, with the usual local corrections at turning points and singular points.

De Broglie's matter-wave picture is the historical bridge between a particle clock and a wave phase [10,11]. It begins with an internal periodicity tied to the particle's proper time and then introduces an associated phase wave. For a free particle, the wave packet has group velocity equal to the particle velocity v , while the phase wave has phase velocity c^2/v ; along the particle path the wave phase remains in harmony with the proper-time clock. Standard wave mechanics and semiclassical quantization then make this associated wave phase the object whose global consistency selects bound states.

This paper separates those ingredients. It keeps the proper-time clock and the loop-closure idea, but asks how far they go before a matter wave is postulated. The closing phase below is not first assumed to be the phase of a matter-wave amplitude. It is the slow laboratory envelope of a localized clock signal. The action integral appears because special relativity makes a comoving clock lag behind laboratory time, and for slow Kepler motion that lag is proportional to $\int v^2 dt$, equivalently to $\int \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r}$. Thus the paper keeps the familiar closure structure, but gives the phase being closed a different physical origin.

The proposed answer is an internal clock. By this we mean a localized oscillatory part of the charge together with its near electromagnetic field, treated as one field-dressed object. The clock is not a little mechanical gear inside the electron. It is an effective finite-size description of unresolved charge-plus-near-field structure. The detailed source model used later is a regulated Maxwell–Lorentz model, but the first step is simpler: once a localized clock is comoving with the charge, Lorentz covariance fixes its phase law,

$$\phi(t) = \omega_0 \tau(t), \quad \dot{\phi} = \omega_0 \frac{d\tau}{dt}. \quad (1)$$

The clock advances in proper time τ . Laboratory time t enters because radiation frequencies are measured in the nucleus frame.

For a slow Coulomb orbit, proper time lags laboratory time by the familiar kinetic term. After removing the main laboratory-frequency clock line, the remaining slow phase is

$$\phi_{\text{slow}}(t) = \omega_0 [\tau(t) - t] \simeq -\frac{\omega_0}{2c^2} \int v^2(t) dt. \quad (2)$$

Using $\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = \mu v^2 dt$, this is an action phase. Thus the internal clock accumulates, around orbital returns, the same kind of phase that appears in semiclassical action quantization. The action unit supplied by the clock is

$$J_{\tau 0} = \frac{2\mu c^2}{\omega_0}. \quad (3)$$

This paper does not derive the empirical value $J_{\tau 0} = \hbar$. It shows what follows once such a clock and action unit are present.

A bound Coulomb orbit has two independent returns. The radius goes from pericenter to apocenter and back, and the orbital angle completes a circuit. Requiring the transported clock phase to close on both returns, with the standard radial turning-point and Coulomb-origin half-shifts, gives

$$J_r = \left(n_r + \frac{1}{2}\right) J_{\tau 0}, \quad J_\theta = \left(\ell + \frac{1}{2}\right) J_{\tau 0}. \quad (4)$$

Therefore

$$J_{\text{Kep}} = J_r + J_\theta = (n_r + \ell + 1)J_{\tau 0} = nJ_{\tau 0}, \quad (5)$$

and the Coulomb Hamiltonian gives

$$E_n = -\frac{\mu \kappa_C^2}{2n^2 J_{\tau 0}^2}. \quad (6)$$

This is the central chain of the paper.

The physical picture is simply this: carry an internal clock around the two returns of a Kepler orbit and require its slow phase to return consistently. Later sections translate that picture into the standard language of loop phases, action variables, and narrow frequency lines.

Main claim. Given a field-dressed charge with a long-lived internal clock whose phase advances as $\omega_0 \tau$, the slow proper-time lag accumulated on a Kepler orbit is proportional to the Kepler action. Closure of that clock phase on the radial and angular returns, with the standard local half-shifts, gives the Coulomb action lattice and therefore the hydrogenic $1/n^2$ energy ladder in the action unit $J_{\tau 0} = 2\mu c^2/\omega_0$.

What is not claimed. The paper does not derive the assumed finite-size field-dressed electron or the existence of the long-lived internal clock from a bare point-charge theory. It does not derive \hbar . It does not solve orbital-band radiative stability, fine structure, Lamb shifts, or measurement statistics. The claim is narrower: it isolates a proper-time closure mechanism for the Coulomb EBK ladder, with all model inputs stated explicitly.

1.1. Novelty relative to wave-based semiclassics

Because the final closure conditions resemble familiar EBK formulas, the novelty must be stated carefully. This paper does not propose a new EBK rule. It proposes a physical source for the phase that is being closed.

In the usual route, one writes a wave phase and requires single-valuedness. Here the transported phase belongs to a localized internal clock attached to the field-dressed charge. The laboratory separation into a main clock line and a slow envelope is not an arbitrary bookkeeping trick. The physical source has the proper-time factor

$$e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)},$$

while outgoing Maxwell modes are decomposed by laboratory-time frequency. Writing the same current as

$$e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)} = e^{-i\omega_0 t} e^{-i\omega_0(\tau(t)-t)} \quad (7)$$

exposes the slow envelope of the actual source near its laboratory clock line. If the clock line is protected only at its central frequency, a non-closing slow envelope shifts spectral weight into nearby detuned lines. Those detuned lines are generically unprotected. Closure is therefore not only a formal single-valuedness condition; in the model studied here it also removes the leading near-line detuning.

1.2. Why a field-dressed clock is a reasonable starting point

Classical point-charge electrodynamics is singular, so the paper does not start from an unregulated point charge. It starts from a finite-size, Lorentz-covariant Maxwell–Lorentz source used as an effective description of the charge and its near-field dressing. This is a modeling input, not a derived electron structure.

The only feature needed from this source is a long-lived localized oscillation that can act as the clock. One concrete way this can happen is familiar in finite electromagnetic sources: two different internal current patterns can radiate into the same far-field dipole channel, and their far-field contributions can cancel at one frequency. In the technical model below these are the ordinary electric-dipole channel and its toroidal electric-parity partner, often denoted $E1 \oplus T1$ [17,20]. The cancellation is the anapole root [19]. For the main argument, the consequence is what matters: a stable localized clock line can be protected at one laboratory frequency, while nearby detuned lines generally are not protected.

All microscopic short-distance details are absorbed into effective parameters. If a proposed field-dressed source has no such long-lived clock line, the mechanism does not apply. This is an explicit physical assumption, not a hidden quantization rule.

1.3. The traditional wave-based route: de Broglie and action closure

De Broglie's phase-harmony picture contains two phases that agree along the particle path [10,11]. The first is the proper-time clock,

$$\phi_{\text{int}} = \omega_0 \tau. \quad (8)$$

The second is an associated matter-wave phase. For a free particle moving at speed v , the usual relations $E = \hbar\omega$ and $p = \hbar k$ give a wave packet whose group velocity is $d\omega/dk = v$, while the phase velocity is $\omega/k = E/p = c^2/v$. This phase velocity is not a signal speed; it is the kinematic phase speed needed for the plane-wave phase $(Et - \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})/\hbar$ to stay in phase with the internal proper-time clock along the particle trajectory.

The bound-state use of this idea then makes the associated wave phase the object whose global consistency is imposed. In wave mechanics the wavefunction must be regular and single-valued. In semiclassical language, for integrable motion, this gives the standard Einstein–Brillouin–Keller (EBK) action conditions [1–4]

$$\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{q} = 2\pi\hbar \left(n_i + \frac{\nu_i}{4} \right), \quad (9)$$

where γ_i are independent cycles and ν_i are the usual defect indices.

The present paper keeps de Broglie's proper-time clock but changes the order of explanation. It does not first postulate a matter-wave phase S/\hbar . It begins with a localized clock phase $\omega_0 \tau$, removes the main laboratory clock line, and asks what phase remains in the slow envelope. The answer is an action phase. The familiar EBK closure conditions are therefore recovered, but they are read as consistency conditions for an internal clock envelope rather than as the starting single-valuedness condition for a matter wave.

1.4. Our route: internal clock, Kepler returns, and leakage selection

We keep the first ingredient of de Broglie's picture, the proper-time clock, but do not start with a matter wave. Instead the clock is supplied by the field-dressed Maxwell–Lorentz source summarized above and developed in Appendix C. Once the clock is localized and comoving, its phase advances in proper time. For slow Coulomb motion, the slow clock phase is proportional to the mechanical action accumulated around closed returns.

The local half-shifts are not new physics introduced by hand for hydrogen. They are the standard local defects of a returned oscillatory object: the radial turning-point slip and the Coulomb-origin, or Langer, half-shift. With those universal slips included, closure on the radial and angular returns gives Eq. (4). The Coulomb Hamiltonian then gives Eq. (6).

The remaining physical question is why non-closing clock histories should be disfavored. Here frequency-local protection matters. The clock line is protected at ω_0 , but a

return mismatch shifts spectral weight to nearby frequencies $\omega_0 + \Delta$. Because the protection zero is simple, the leakage is quadratic in small detuning. Sections 8 and Appendix A show this in the narrowband regime. A full kinetic attractor theory is not claimed.

Relation to other quantization viewpoints. Mathematically, the closed-loop phase is related to geometric phases on invariant tori, including Hannay's classical angle holonomy and Berry's quantum phase factors [5,6]. It is also close to geometric/action-angle quantization, where loop periods determine allowed actions [7,8]. The physical claim here is narrower and more concrete: the phase is supplied by proper-time transport of a localized field-dressed clock, and frequency-local radiative protection gives a cost for detuning the clock line.

1.5. Scope

We isolate one mechanism: closure of the phase of a field-dressed internal clock on a planar Kepler orbit. Planarity is enough for the energy ladder because the Coulomb energy depends only on the principal action. The full three-dimensional degeneracy structure is not derived here.

We do *not* solve stability of matter, orbital-band radiative quietness, fine structure, Lamb shifts, QED corrections, or measurement statistics. Identifying $J_{\tau 0} \equiv \hbar$ is an external empirical calibration, not part of the clock-closure geometry.

1.6. Inputs and what they produce

The argument uses the following standing inputs. They are stated up front so the boundary between model input and derived consequence is visible.

1. **Finite field-dressed source:** the electron is represented by a finite-size, Lorentz-covariant effective source, not by an unregulated point charge. The microscopic origin of this source is an effective-model input; Appendix C records one Maxwell–Lorentz realization.
2. **Stable internal clock line:** the finite source supports a localized high-frequency oscillation with clock frequency ω_0 . In the concrete realization this line comes from the retained $E1 \oplus T1$ electric-parity channel after renormalizing the reactive self-field into positive effective inertias and stiffnesses.
3. **Frequency-local protection:** the clock line is long-lived at ω_0 , its action is approximately fixed on slow Kepler time scales, and its leading dipole radiation coefficient vanishes at that line while nearby detuned lines generically leak.

4. **Slow–fast separation:** $\Omega \ll \omega_0$, so averaging over the fast clock phase is meaningful and the Kepler variables evolve slowly compared with the internal clock.
5. **Universal defect patching:** the radial Maslov slip and the Langer half-shift are imported as universal local patching data for the transported return object. These standard defects are not derived from the Maxwell kernel.
6. **Dominance of the proper-time contribution:** the phase-drift 1-form can be written $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_\tau + \delta\mathcal{A}$, where \mathcal{A}_τ is the universal proper-time piece derived in Section 4. We assume $|\oint_{\gamma_i} \delta\mathcal{A}| \ll |\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}_\tau|$ on the generator cycles.
7. **Weak perturbations/noise/dissipation:** over long times the slow phases are not perfectly frozen, so the system samples loops that wind around the two generator cycles. This is used only to justify why generator closures matter physically.

Item	Input	Output
Finite field-dressed source	assumed effective near-field dressing	gives a nonsingular place for a localized clock degree of freedom
Internal clock line	long-lived oscillation at ω_0	localized proper-time phase $\omega_0\tau$
Proper-time lag	special-relativistic kinematics	action phase $-J_{\tau 0}^{-1} \oint \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r}$
Defect slips	standard Maslov/Langer local patching	half-shifted EBK lattice
Action scale	calibrated by experiment, $J_{\tau 0} = \hbar$	hydrogenic numerical spectrum

1.7. Notation snapshot

We use μ for the reduced electron–nucleus mass and κ_C for the Coulomb coupling. The Kepler actions are J_r and J_θ , with principal action $J_{\text{Kep}} = J_r + J_\theta$. The internal clock frequency is ω_0 , and the corresponding action unit is $J_{\tau 0} = 2\mu c^2/\omega_0$. The two Kepler return angles are α_r for the radial oscillation and θ for the angular circuit.

1.8. Roadmap

Section 2 sets up the slow Kepler variables and the internal clock line. Section 3 explains why the clock phase advances in proper time and why laboratory demodulation exposes a physical slow envelope. Section 4 shows that this envelope is the Kepler action one-form in the slow limit. Section 5 states the closed-loop phase condition. Section 6 adds the radial and angular defect slips. Section 7 derives the Coulomb action lattice and the $1/n^2$

ladder. Section 8 explains why non-closing clock histories leak near-line spectral weight. Section 9 states limitations and expected extensions.

1.9. Warm-up: why a non-closing clock creates sidebands

Before using the two-return Kepler orbit, consider a single slow periodic coordinate with period T . The physical current contains the proper-time clock factor $e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)}$. A laboratory detector, however, decomposes radiation by laboratory time, so we write

$$e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)} = e^{-i\omega_0 t} e^{-i\omega_0(\tau(t)-t)}.$$

The first factor is the clock line at ω_0 . The second is the slow envelope caused by time dilation. If that envelope returns to the same value after one slow period, it does not move the clock line into a shifted nearby frequency. If the envelope returns with a phase mismatch, the laboratory spectrum gains detuned sidebands. The Kepler calculation below applies this same idea to two independent returns, with the standard Coulomb half-shifts included.

2. Kepler motion plus a localized clock

2.1. The two returns of a bound Kepler orbit

The planar Kepler problem is integrable. A bound orbit is conveniently described by action–angle variables

$$(J_r, \alpha_r) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{T}, \quad (J_\theta, \theta) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{T},$$

where θ is the azimuthal angle and α_r is a radial phase (both 2π -periodic).¹ Fixing (J_r, J_θ) fixes the Kepler torus; (θ, α_r) label points on that torus.

The charge also carries a fast localized clock, described at the slow–fast level by an action–phase pair (J_+, ϕ) . The clock frequency is

$$\omega_0 = \frac{\partial H_{\text{int}}}{\partial J_+},$$

and the orbital frequency scale is Ω . The regime of interest is $\Omega \ll \omega_0$. Any narrowband oscillator admits such an action–phase description: J_+ measures the oscillation energy

¹ Any standard Kepler action–angle set can be used. One convenient choice is the Delaunay set, where α_r may be taken as the mean anomaly (a 2π -periodic radial phase). Different choices are related by integer linear transformations of the angles and do not change the generator-period closed-loop phases central to this paper.

scale and ϕ is the phase, defined modulo 2π . Later we treat ω_0 as a constant, evaluated on the long-lived clock state.

The clock line is not simply postulated. Appendix C gives one Maxwell–Lorentz realization. The short version is this: a finite field-dressed source can contain a localized internal electromagnetic motion. Its reactive near-field dynamics can make this motion an oscillator, while its radiating part can cancel at one laboratory frequency. That protected frequency is the long-lived clock line used below.

The cancellation is local in frequency: nearby detuned lines are generally not canceled and can leak power. In a locked narrowband regime the bright internal coordinate, denoted $q_+(t)$ in Section 8, is well approximated by a harmonic oscillator and can be written in action–angle form (J_+, ϕ) . Other multipoles and radiation driven by orbital acceleration are separate issues; we do not model them here, and we return to what this implies for scope in Subsection 9.2.

2.2. What it means for the clock line to be long-lived

The phase-closure derivation of the action lattice, Sections 3–7, uses only the proper-time phase law and Kepler dynamics. The later selection argument, Section 8 and Appendix A, adds a separate modeling input: the clock line is protected at ω_0 , while nearby detuned lines generally leak. We call this *frequency-local protection*. In the source model this protection is represented by a frequency-local anapole-style cancellation.

The basic idea is ordinary destructive interference in a far-field radiation channel. A finite source can contain internal current patterns whose distant radiation amplitudes have the same outgoing pattern but opposite phase at one frequency. At that frequency the radiated field can cancel even though energy remains stored in the near zone. For the present paper this cancellation is not a microscopic derivation of electron structure, and it is not a claim that the source is exactly nonradiating in every channel. It is an explicit effective assumption used to model a protected clock line; Appendix C gives one Maxwell–Lorentz realization of that assumption.

At retained electric-parity $l = 1$ order the far field of a localized internal source with effective size R ($kR \ll 1$) is controlled by a single polar vector. A convenient package for that radiating coefficient is

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = \mathbf{d}(\omega) + ik(\omega) \mathbf{T}_{\text{eff}}(\omega), \quad k(\omega) = \frac{\omega}{c}, \quad \mathbf{T}_{\text{eff}} := \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{T}_{\text{src}}, \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{d} is the ordinary electric dipole moment and \mathbf{T}_{src} is the toroidal-dipole source moment (so that $k\mathbf{T}_{\text{eff}}$ has dipole units; the convention is recorded in Appendix C). In the radiation zone the electric and toroidal dipoles share the same $l = 1$ angular pattern; only the combined coefficient \mathbf{d}_{eff} is fixed by the far field [17].

Definition (protected clock line). Fix an outgoing electric-parity $l = 1$ channel. The internal clock line is protected at ω_0 in that channel if

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}.$$

The protection is frequency-local if this zero is simple: $\partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}|_{\omega_0} \neq \mathbf{0}$. Then for small detuning Δ ,

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0 + \Delta) = \Delta \partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}|_{\omega_0} + O(\Delta^2), \quad P_\infty(\omega_0 + \Delta) = O(\Delta^2)$$

at dipole order, because $P_\infty \propto |\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}|^2$ (Eq. (53)).

The only consequence used later is the quadratic detuning law: if phase mismatch shifts near-line spectral weight away from ω_0 , it leaks power even though the clock line itself is protected.

A protected line is not perfectly nonradiating. Higher multipoles, damping, and noise give the clock line a finite half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) Γ_0 in angular frequency. The selection argument is sharpest when the near-line comb is spectrally resolved, i.e. when Γ_0 is not larger than the orbital frequency scale Ω (Section 8). We also use frequency-local protection only inside a detuning window $|\Delta| \leq \Delta_{\text{loc}}$ where the Taylor law in the definition box is accurate. A conservative choice is

$$\Delta_{\text{loc}} := \min\{\Delta_{\text{int}}, c/R\}, \tag{11}$$

where Δ_{int} is the separation from ω_0 to the nearest other internal resonance and R is the internal size scale controlling the near-zone/multipole expansion. Throughout we assume $\Omega \ll \Delta_{\text{loc}}$, so the near-line sidebands relevant for mismatch lie inside the protection window.

2.2.1. One concrete Maxwell–Lorentz clock model

The main derivation does not require the reader to accept a microscopic model of the electron. It requires only a long-lived internal clock line. This subsection records one finite-source realization of such a line; the detailed algebra is in Appendix C.

The retained internal motion contains two electric-parity $l = 1$ source channels: an electric dipole coordinate $E1$ and a toroidal partner $T1$. The principal-value part of the self-field gives a local coupled-oscillator block. After diagonalization, one hybrid oscillator is the bright clock mode, denoted q_+ , at frequency ω_0 . The light-shell part is rank one at this order: radiation couples only to

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega) = \kappa_e \mathbf{q}_e(\omega) + ik(\omega) \kappa_t \mathbf{q}_t(\omega), \tag{12}$$

so a phase-locked internal state can satisfy $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}$. Because this is an interference

zero of a smooth coefficient, detuned lines $\omega_0 + \Delta$ are generally unprotected to leading order.

Proposition 1 (Field-dressed clock interface). Consider a finite Lorentz-covariant Maxwell–Lorentz source whose electron current is decomposed into a transported charge current and a localized neutral internal current in the same near-zone region. Retain the electric-parity $l = 1$ internal motion, represented by an electric dipole amplitude $\mathbf{d} = \kappa_e \mathbf{q}_e$ and a toroidal electric-parity amplitude $\mathbf{Q} = \kappa_q \mathbf{q}_t$. Assume the principal-value part of the self-kernel is renormalized to a stable local quadratic form. Then:

1. the reactive internal dynamics contains a local $E1 \oplus T1$ oscillator block with two hybrid modes ω_{\pm} ;
2. the light-shell electric-parity $l = 1$ loss is rank one and depends only on $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = \mathbf{d}(\omega) + i(\omega/c^2)\mathbf{Q}(\omega)$;
3. a phase-locked internal state can be protected at a clock line $\omega_0 = \omega_+$ by the anapole condition $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}$;
4. once this localized state is written as a comoving worldline degree of freedom, its action–angle phase obeys

$$\frac{d\phi}{d\tau} = \frac{\partial H_{\text{int}}}{\partial J_+} \simeq \omega_0, \quad \dot{\phi} = \omega_0 \frac{d\tau}{dt}.$$

Thus the proper-time clock used below is obtained at the finite-source Maxwell–Lorentz interface level. The proposition does not derive the finite source itself, the existence of the internal current model from a bare point charge, or the action calibration $J_{\tau 0} = \hbar$.

2.3. Effective slow Lagrangian

After averaging over the fast clock phase (made possible by $\Omega \ll \omega_0$), the reduced dynamics of the slow Kepler torus variables and the clock action–phase pair remains first order: it is of the canonical form “ $J\dot{\vartheta} - H$ ” up to total derivatives. At leading order in the slow rates $(\dot{\theta}, \dot{\alpha}_r)$, any surviving slow–fast coupling that affects the clock phase can be organized as a term linear in the slow rates and proportional to the clock action J_+ . Equivalently, it is J_+ times a 1-form on the slow torus. Other averaged contributions either (i) do not depend on the slow rates and simply shift the Hamiltonian, or (ii) enter as higher-order corrections to the 1-form (discussed below as $\delta\mathcal{A}$). We therefore write the general averaged slow Lagrangian as

$$\boxed{L_{\text{slow}} = J_r \dot{\alpha}_r + J_{\theta} \dot{\theta} + J_+ \dot{\phi} - H_{\text{Kep}}(J_r, J_{\theta}) - H_{\text{int}}(J_+) + J_+ G_{\theta}(J_r, J_{\theta}) \dot{\theta} + J_+ G_r(J_r, J_{\theta}) \dot{\alpha}_r.} \tag{13}$$

Proposition 2 (What the slow–fast interface assumes). Eq. (13) is the structural “interface” input of the mechanism: it is the most general first-order slow Lagrangian compatible with (i) a 2π -periodic clock phase ϕ and (ii) adiabatic averaging over the fast clock cycle, when we keep only terms *linear* in the slow rates $(\dot{\theta}, \dot{\alpha}_r)$.

The transport data are encoded by the 1-form $\mathcal{A} = G_\theta d\theta + G_r d\alpha_r$. To make explicit what is discarded and why it does not affect the *generator periods* at the retained order, we note:

1. Terms that survive the averaging but do *not* depend on $(\dot{\theta}, \dot{\alpha}_r)$ only shift the slow Hamiltonian and/or the clock frequency; they do not contribute directly to the loop integrals $\oint \mathcal{A}$.
2. Any velocity-linear piece that is a *zero-period gauge term* on the torus, i.e. of the form $d\chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$ with χ single-valued on \mathbb{T}^2 , can be absorbed into a slow-dependent phase convention $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi$; this does not change any closed-loop phase.
3. All remaining averaged couplings that are linear in slow rates contribute additively to \mathcal{A} . In the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction these appear as a correction $\delta\mathcal{A}$ beyond the universal proper-time piece \mathcal{A}_τ ; their generator periods $\oint_{\gamma_i} \delta\mathcal{A}$ can, in principle, shift closure. Our standing assumption is that these periods are small compared to those of \mathcal{A}_τ (Subsection 1.6).
4. Terms that are quadratic (or higher) in the slow rates are dropped in Eq. (13). In an adiabatic expansion they are suppressed by at least one power of Ω/ω_0 and/or v/c . They can renormalize slow dynamics, but their contribution to the clock return phase over a generator cycle is higher order than the leading $O(v^2/c^2)$ proper-time closed-loop phase used for the Coulomb ladder in this paper.

Finally, Eq. (13) is to be read *on* the stable protected clock mode: at leading order μ and ω_0 are treated as fixed mode parameters and G_θ, G_r are taken as functions of (J_r, J_θ) only. Any residual dependence on J_+ (through $\mu(J_+)$, anharmonicity, or slow drift of the nearly fixed clock action) produces corrections that are absorbed into $\delta\mathcal{A}$ and are beyond the leading closed-loop phase periods used here.

A canonical derivation of this interface structure and its realization in the reduced Maxwell–Lorentz model are summarized in Appendix E.

The last line in Eq. (13) is the key transport term: it couples the fast clock to the slow angles through two coefficient functions G_θ and G_r . Equivalently, it is $J_+ \mathcal{A}(\dot{\gamma})$ where $\mathcal{A} = G_\theta d\theta + G_r d\alpha_r$ is a 1-form on the Kepler torus. A slow-dependent rephasing $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$ shifts \mathcal{A} by an exact 1-form ($\mathcal{A} \mapsto \mathcal{A} - d\chi$) without changing any loop integral $\oint \mathcal{A}$. In the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction the full \mathcal{A} can be computed; in Sections 3–4 we derive the universal leading piece supplied by proper time.

For Coulomb motion,

$$H_{\text{Kep}}(J_r, J_\theta) = -\frac{\mu \kappa_C^2}{2(J_r + J_\theta)^2}, \quad \kappa_C := \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0}, \quad (14)$$

so the Kepler energy depends only on the *principal action*

$$J_{\text{Kep}} := J_r + J_\theta. \quad (15)$$

Kepler actions in Coulomb (for quick checking). For a bound Coulomb orbit ($E < 0$) with mechanical angular momentum magnitude L one may evaluate the radial action integral explicitly and obtain

$$J_r = \frac{\mu\kappa_C}{\sqrt{-2\mu E}} - L, \quad J_\theta = L \quad \Rightarrow \quad J_{\text{Kep}} = J_r + J_\theta = \frac{\mu\kappa_C}{\sqrt{-2\mu E}}. \quad (16)$$

Here J_θ is the classical angular action (equal to the mechanical L for smooth central motion); the Langer defect discussed later affects the quantization offset, not the classical Kepler Hamiltonian. Solving for E recovers Eq. (14). Equivalently, in terms of the semi-major axis a one has $J_{\text{Kep}} = \sqrt{\mu\kappa_C a}$ and the usual Kepler relation $E = -\kappa_C/(2a)$.

2.4. How slow orbital motion changes the clock phase

Varying Eq. (13) with respect to J_+ gives the clock phase equation

$$\dot{\phi} = \omega_0(J_+) - G_\theta(J_r, J_\theta) \dot{\theta} - G_r(J_r, J_\theta) \dot{\alpha}_r, \quad \omega_0(J_+) := \frac{\partial H_{\text{int}}}{\partial J_+}. \quad (17)$$

Stable-clock-mode remark. Eq. (17) is written in the interface form where G_θ, G_r depend on the slow actions (J_r, J_θ) only. If in a more complete reduction these coefficients inherit a weak J_+ -dependence (for example through $\mu(J_+)$ or through anharmonicity), then varying L_{slow} would produce additional terms proportional to $\dot{\theta} \partial_{J_+} G_\theta + \dot{\alpha}_r \partial_{J_+} G_r$. In the long-lived protected regime we work on a stable clock mode $J_+ \simeq J_+^*$ and evaluate the drift coefficients on that mode; any residual J_+ -dependence produces higher-order corrections that are grouped into $\delta\mathcal{A}$.

This is the “phase drift rule”: after subtracting the trivial ω_0 advance, the clock phase drifts by an amount proportional to the slow angular rates. It is useful to package the drift by the 1-form

$$\mathcal{A} := G_\theta d\theta + G_r d\alpha_r. \quad (18)$$

If $\gamma(t) = (\theta(t), \alpha_r(t))$ is any slow path on the torus, then $\mathcal{A}(\dot{\gamma}) = G_\theta \dot{\theta} + G_r \dot{\alpha}_r$. The geometric phase picked up on a closed loop γ is

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{geom}}(\gamma) = -\oint_\gamma \mathcal{A}. \quad (19)$$

This is the closed-loop phase: a return error that depends only on the loop. In geometric language it is a holonomy, but the calculation below uses only the loop integral.

A remaining freedom is the choice of phase zero. One may redefine the clock phase by adding any smooth function $\chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$: $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$. This shifts the drift 1-form by an exact differential, $\mathcal{A} \mapsto \mathcal{A} - d\chi$. Because $\oint_\gamma d\chi = 0$ on any closed loop, the return phase in Eq. (19) is unchanged. A 1-form with this transformation property is often called a “connection.” Here we use \mathcal{A} simply as a concrete phase-drift rule and focus on its loop integrals.

3. Why the internal-clock phase advances in proper time

A natural question is: why should ϕ tick in τ rather than in t ? In our framework this is not an extra assumption; it is forced by Lorentz covariance for a comoving internal clock.

3.1. Worldline clock action

A localized internal system defined in the instantaneous rest frame admits a Lorentz-scalar worldline description. The invariant parameter on the worldline is proper time, $d\tau = \sqrt{dx^\mu dx_\mu}/c$. Therefore the leading local effective action has the schematic form

$$S = \int d\tau L_{\text{eff}}(\text{internal DOFs}), \tag{20}$$

supplemented by higher-derivative or nonlocal terms generated by integrating out the electromagnetic field. The reduced Maxwell–Lorentz construction behind the interface is summarized in Appendix C.

For an internal action–angle pair (J_+, ϕ) , the reparametrization-invariant canonical term is $J_+ d\phi$. Thus the minimal “clock” sector is

$$S_{\text{clock}} = \int d\tau \left(J_+ \frac{d\phi}{d\tau} - H_{\text{int}}(J_+) \right). \tag{21}$$

Varying J_+ in Eq. (21) gives the comoving phase law

$$\frac{d\phi}{d\tau} = \frac{\partial H_{\text{int}}}{\partial J_+} = \omega_0(J_+),$$

so ϕ is accumulated in proper time.

3.2. Laboratory time, spectra, and the time-dilation envelope

Passing to laboratory time uses $d\tau = (d\tau/dt) dt$. The canonical term is reparametrization invariant:

$$J_+ \frac{d\phi}{d\tau} d\tau = J_+ d\phi = J_+ \dot{\phi} dt.$$

Thus the lab-time clock Lagrangian is

$$L_{\text{clock}}(t) = J_+ \dot{\phi} - H_{\text{int}}(J_+) \frac{d\tau}{dt}. \tag{22}$$

Varying J_+ gives

$$\dot{\phi} = \frac{\partial H_{\text{int}}}{\partial J_+} \frac{d\tau}{dt} = \omega_0(J_+) \frac{d\tau}{dt} \simeq \omega_0 \frac{d\tau}{dt}. \tag{23}$$

This is the proper-time phase law of one physical clock. Laboratory time enters for a different reason: outgoing Maxwell fields are labeled by Fourier frequency with respect to the inertial laboratory time, here the nucleus rest-frame time. Radiated power and the anapole cancellation are therefore statements about the lab-time spectrum of the current.

In the protected clock state the actual near-line current contains the factor $e^{-i\phi(t)} = e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)}$. Factoring it as

$$e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)} = e^{-i\omega_0 t} e^{-i\tilde{\phi}(t)}, \quad \tilde{\phi}(t) := \omega_0(\tau(t) - t), \tag{24}$$

does not introduce a second clock. It separates the same physical source into the clock line at which $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega_0) = 0$ and a slow envelope whose Fourier content creates nearby lab-frequency sidebands. Because the anapole zero is frequency-local, those sidebands are not protected unless the envelope closes in the appropriate sense. This is why the demodulated phase is a physical quantity in the present mechanism.

For nonrelativistic motion, $d\tau/dt = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = 1 - \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + O(v^4/c^4)$, so Eq. (22) becomes

$$L_{\text{clock}}(t) = J_+ \dot{\phi} - H_{\text{int}}(J_+) + \frac{H_{\text{int}}(J_+)}{2c^2} v^2 + O\left(\frac{v^4}{c^4}\right). \tag{25}$$

The third term is the universal slow-fast cross term. Equivalently, Eq. (24) gives the slow envelope increment

$$d\tilde{\phi} = \omega_0(d\tau - dt) = -\frac{\omega_0}{2c^2} v^2 dt + O(v^4/c^4). \tag{26}$$

The nontrivial content of the next section is what this lab-time envelope phase becomes when expressed in action-angle variables: it becomes the geometric drift 1-form \mathcal{A} .

4. From time dilation to action around the orbit

The time-dilation term in Eq. (25) is proportional to v^2 . To turn that scalar into a transport rule on the Kepler torus, we use two standard identities. First, in the electrostatic Kepler truncation of the orbital sector (no vector potential), we may take $L_{\text{Kep}} = \frac{1}{2}\mu v^2 + \kappa_C/r$, so the canonical momentum is also the mechanical momentum, $\mathbf{p} := \partial L_{\text{Kep}}/\partial \dot{\mathbf{r}} = \mu \dot{\mathbf{r}}$ (any additional canonical one-form terms generated by electromagnetic dressing are grouped into $\delta\mathcal{A}$, Sec. 4.2). Hence

$$\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = \mu v^2 dt, \quad v := |\dot{\mathbf{r}}|. \tag{27}$$

Second, on an integrable Kepler torus one can choose action–angle variables (J_θ, θ) and (J_r, α_r) so that the actions are the loop integrals of the canonical one-form:

$$\oint_{\gamma_\theta} \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = 2\pi J_\theta, \quad \oint_{\gamma_r} \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = 2\pi J_r.$$

In such variables the canonical one-form can always be written as the sum of an “action–angle part” plus an exact differential (a gauge term) that does not contribute to any closed-loop integral on the torus:

$$\boxed{\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = J_\theta d\theta + J_r d\alpha_r + dF.} \tag{28}$$

Here $F(\theta, \alpha_r)$ is a generating function defined on the universal cover; changing the angle chart can shift F by linear functions of the angles, which only adds integer multiples of 2π to generator integrals and therefore only relabels the integers in the closure conditions. In the slow Lagrangian such an exact term can be absorbed by a slow-dependent phase convention for the clock, $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$.

4.1. Matching the time-dilation phase to action

The Lorentz-covariant clock premise says that the clock phase advances with proper time. In laboratory time this is Eq. (23), obtained by varying the worldline clock action in Eq. (21). Expanding $d\tau/dt = 1 - \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + O(v^4/c^4)$ gives the leading laboratory-time slip

$$\dot{\phi} = \omega_0 - \frac{\omega_0}{2c^2} v^2 + O(v^4/c^4), \quad (\omega_0 \text{ evaluated on the stable clock mode}). \tag{29}$$

After demodulating the trivial ω_0 advance, the remaining drift is therefore

$$d(\phi - \omega_0 t) = -\frac{\omega_0}{2c^2} v^2 dt + O(v^4/c^4). \tag{30}$$

Using $\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = \mu v^2 dt$ (Eq. (27)) and the action–angle decomposition $\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = J_\theta d\theta + J_r d\alpha_r + dF$ (Eq. (28)), we obtain

$$d(\phi - \omega_0 t) = -\frac{\omega_0}{2\mu c^2} \left(J_\theta d\theta + J_r d\alpha_r \right) - \frac{\omega_0}{2\mu c^2} dF + O(v^4/c^4). \tag{31}$$

The dF term is a zero-period gauge term on the chosen action–angle chart, so it contributes no closed-loop phase and may be absorbed by a slow-dependent choice of clock phase zero.

Defining the action unit

$$\boxed{J_{\tau 0} := \frac{2\mu c^2}{\omega_0},} \tag{32}$$

we identify the universal leading proper-time transport 1-form as

$$\boxed{\mathcal{A}_\tau = \frac{J_\theta}{J_{\tau 0}} d\theta + \frac{J_r}{J_{\tau 0}} d\alpha_r \quad (\text{up to a zero-period gauge term}).} \tag{33}$$

The key structural point is that the lab-time envelope drift is controlled by the *single* scalar $v^2 = \dot{r}^2$. Consequently it couples through the canonical one-form $\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r}$ and weights both torus generators with the same prefactor. This is the origin of the “one-scale” form in Eq. (33) with a single action unit $J_{\tau 0}$. A generic slow–fast coupling in the interface Lagrangian of Eq. (13) would allow independent coefficients multiplying $d\theta$ and $d\alpha_r$, leading to two unrelated generator scales; proper time is special because it produces $v^2 dt$ and therefore $J_\theta d\theta + J_r d\alpha_r$ with a common prefactor.

4.2. Higher-order contributions to the drift 1-form

The proper-time calculation above gives the leading drift 1-form, but a full Maxwell–Lorentz reduction need not produce *only* this contribution. It is therefore useful to write

$$\boxed{\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_\tau + \delta\mathcal{A}}, \tag{34}$$

where $\delta\mathcal{A}$ collects all other averaged slow–fast couplings that are linear in $(\dot{\theta}, \dot{\alpha}_r)$.

In the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction, such terms arise from subleading worldline/near-zone operators (magnetostatic/Darwin-type dressing of the orbital momentum, finite-size corrections, and adiabatic corrections to the stable internal eigenmode) and are suppressed by at least one small parameter among v^2/c^2 , Ω/ω_0 , and $(k_0 R)^2$. Appendix C gives the source hierarchy used here; standard effective-field-theory power counting for radiative systems gives the same symmetry-based organizing logic for subleading worldline operators [27]. Representative estimates are collected in Appendix F.

A concise way to state this “proper-time dominance” assumption is to factor out the leading one-scale periods: for each generator γ_i one may write

$$\oint_{\gamma_i} \delta\mathcal{A} = 2\pi \frac{J_i}{J_{\tau 0}} \varepsilon_i, \quad |\varepsilon_i| \ll 1, \quad i \in \{\theta, r\},$$

with dimensionless ε_i controlled by the small ratios that suppress subleading operators (e.g. v^2/c^2 , Ω/ω_0 , and $(k_0 R)^2$ on the stable protected clock state). If the ε_i were not small, there would be no reason for the two generator periods to share a common action unit: generic slow–fast couplings would produce two unrelated scales rather than the single $J_{\tau 0}$ in Eq. (33). In this sense the appearance of a one-scale EBK lattice is itself a diagnostic of the proper-time dominated regime. In any concrete completion, estimating the ε_i provides a potential falsifier: if no regime exists in which $|\varepsilon_i| \ll 1$ while a long-lived protected clock line persists, then the present mechanism does not apply.

For phase closure, the only gauge-invariant data in $\delta\mathcal{A}$ are its *generator periods*. Exact pieces ($\delta\mathcal{A} = d\chi$ with χ single-valued on the torus) integrate to zero and may be absorbed by rephasing the clock; only nonzero periods can shift the closure conditions. The working

regime assumed throughout is therefore

$$\left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \delta \mathcal{A} \right| \ll \left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}_\tau \right| = 2\pi \frac{J_i}{J_{\tau 0}}, \quad i \in \{\theta, r\}. \quad (35)$$

When Eq. (35) holds, $\delta \mathcal{A}$ deforms the EBK lattice only perturbatively (at the correction scale discussed in Section 9.4).

Outside this regime (for example, relativistic motion, breakdown of the near-zone hierarchy $k_0 R \ll 1$, or internal near-degeneracy $\Delta_{\text{int}} \sim \Omega$ that spoils adiabatic separation) the one-scale lattice need not emerge, and the present mechanism is not claimed there.

4.3. Remark: relation to Hannay/Berry phases

Mathematically, Eq. (19) is a geometric phase: it is the same kind of object that appears as a Hannay angle (classically) or a Berry phase (quantum mechanically) [4–6]. At fixed actions (J_r, J_θ) the leading proper-time form is *flat*: $d\mathcal{A}_\tau = 0$, so its closed-loop phases depend only on the winding numbers on the torus. Curvature enters only through action dependence and/or through corrections $\delta \mathcal{A}$. The nonstandard point here is the *physical role*: the phase is a real internal clock, not an abstract wavefunction phase, and global narrowband consistency of a protected clock line turns phase closure into an action quantization rule.

5. Closed-loop clock phase as a consistency condition

5.1. The slow clock phase and its return mismatch

Define the slow clock phase by removing the main laboratory-frequency clock line from the actual proper-time current. Equivalently,

$$e^{-i\phi(t)} = e^{-i \int^t \omega_0(J_+) dt'} e^{-i\tilde{\phi}(t)}, \quad \tilde{\phi}(t) := \phi(t) - \int^t \omega_0(J_+) dt'. \quad (36)$$

The first factor is the laboratory clock line at which protection is imposed. The second is the slow envelope; its laboratory-time Fourier content determines whether nearby sidebands appear. Then Eq. (17) implies

$$\dot{\tilde{\phi}}(t) = -\mathcal{A}(\dot{\gamma}), \quad \Delta \tilde{\phi}(\gamma) = - \oint_\gamma \mathcal{A}.$$

Let γ_θ denote the loop that advances $\theta \mapsto \theta + 2\pi$ at fixed α_r , and γ_r the loop that advances $\alpha_r \mapsto \alpha_r + 2\pi$ at fixed θ . These two loops are the *torus generators*: any closed loop on the (θ, α_r) torus is homotopic to a loop that winds an integer number of times around γ_θ and γ_r .

Define the *defect-corrected slow clock factor* on the slow torus by

$$U(\theta, \alpha_r) := \exp(-i\tilde{\phi}(\theta, \alpha_r)) \exp\left(-i\frac{\nu_\theta}{4}\theta - i\frac{\nu_r}{4}\alpha_r\right), \quad (37)$$

where the integers $(\nu_\theta, \nu_r) \in \mathbb{Z}$ are *defect indices* representing universal discrete phase slips of the demodulated clock acquired at isolated points where the slow transport picture fails (most commonly, turning points). The specific form $\exp(-i\nu_\theta\theta/4 - i\nu_r\alpha_r/4)$ is chosen so that a 2π advance of θ or α_r removes a fixed local slip $\nu_{\theta,r} \pi/2$ from the clock envelope; thus U is the clock factor with these known local slips removed, so that phase closure can be stated as a global single-valuedness condition on U . The values of $\nu_{\theta,r}$ are determined in Sec. 6.

What we mean by “globally monochromatic” and why U lives on the torus At retained dipole order the radiated field in a fixed electric-parity $\ell = 1$ channel is controlled by the corresponding *projected* effective coefficient (Subsection 2.2): for any fixed outgoing polarization direction \hat{e} we may work with the scalar amplitude

$$d_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(t) := \hat{e} \cdot \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(t),$$

since only this channel amplitude enters the dipole power in that channel. For a stable narrowband clock, the internal dynamics is dominated by a clock tone at angular frequency ω_0 , so this channel amplitude admits the standard rotating-wave decomposition

$$d_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(t) \simeq \Re\{d_+ a(t) e^{-i\omega_0 t}\}, \quad (38)$$

where d_+ is a *constant* complex coefficient set by the chosen channel and the internal mode shape, and where the complex envelope $a(t)$ varies only on the slow orbital timescales. Equivalently, reinstating the vector notation, one may write $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(t) \simeq \Re\{\mathbf{d}_+ a(t) e^{-i\omega_0 t}\}$ with \mathbf{d}_+ fixed.

In the slow–fast interface premise, the internal clock action is held approximately fixed while the slow orbital state wanders on the Kepler torus. Thus any slow modulation of the clock envelope can be taken to depend on the slow torus coordinates only. Writing the slow state as $\gamma(t) = (\theta(t), \alpha_r(t)) \in \mathbb{T}^2$, we may therefore express the envelope as

$$a(t) = U(\gamma(t)) = U(\theta(t), \alpha_r(t)),$$

which is precisely the defect-corrected clock factor introduced in Eq. (37). Substituting into Eq. (38) gives the advertised narrowband form along the orbit. Accordingly, “global monochromaticity in the laboratory” becomes a statement about the Fourier content of U on the Kepler torus. This is the precise sense in which phase closure has physical content here: it controls the lab-time spectrum of the actual Maxwell source, not an arbitrary bookkeeping phase.

By “globally monochromatic in the laboratory” we mean: within the frequency window where protection is effective, there are no *resolved* near-line components besides ω_0 . Two logically distinct statements are then in play:

1. *Phase closure* (a boundary-condition statement): the defect-corrected factor $U(\theta, \alpha_r)$ is periodic on both torus generators. Equivalently, it is single-valued on \mathbb{T}^2 , up to the large rephasings discussed below.
2. *Single-line dominance* (a spectral-content statement): even when U is periodic, it can have nontrivial Fourier content on \mathbb{T}^2 , hence sidebands at $\omega_0 + m\Omega_\theta + n\Omega_r$.

Phase closure is therefore a *necessary* condition for an exactly protected clock line at ω_0 once the slow motion explores the torus, but it does not by itself guarantee the absence of other near-line components. The stronger “single line at ω_0 ” statement additionally requires that (after an allowed large rephasing) U be close to constant on \mathbb{T}^2 , so that its $(m, n) = (0, 0)$ Fourier coefficient dominates. We call this additional dynamical requirement the *single-line protected regime*; it is the “single-line smoothness” assumption made explicit in Appendix A. In that regime, a small mismatch produces *excess* near-line leakage dominated by the detuned $(0, 0)$ line.

Lemma 1 (Single-valued clock factor on the torus implies phase closure). If the defect-corrected clock factor U is single-valued on the Kepler torus, in the sense that

$$U(\theta + 2\pi, \alpha_r) = U(\theta, \alpha_r), \quad U(\theta, \alpha_r + 2\pi) = U(\theta, \alpha_r),$$

then the loop integrals of \mathcal{A} satisfy

$$\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A} = 2\pi N_i + \frac{\nu_i \pi}{2}, \quad i \in \{\theta, r\}, \quad N_i \in \mathbb{Z}. \tag{39}$$

Proof. Traversing γ_i changes $\tilde{\phi}$ by $-\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}$ (Eq. (19)). The physical envelope factor $\exp(-i\tilde{\phi})$ therefore contributes $+\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}$, while the defect factor in Eq. (37) removes $\nu_i \pi/2$. Single-valuedness means $\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A} - \nu_i \pi/2 = 2\pi N_i$, which is Eq. (39). \square

Large rephasings and the origin of the integers The phase convention freedom $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$ can be “large”. On the universal cover one may choose $\chi = N_\theta \theta + N_r \alpha_r$ with $N_i \in \mathbb{Z}$, which is multi-valued as a function on \mathbb{T}^2 but has a single-valued differential $d\chi = N_\theta d\theta + N_r d\alpha_r$. Under such a rephasing,

$$\mathcal{A} \mapsto \mathcal{A} - d\chi \implies \oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A} \mapsto \oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A} - 2\pi N_i,$$

while the physical near-line signal is unchanged after the corresponding redefinition of the constant mode coefficient; only the phase convention used to write the envelope has

changed. Thus the integers N_i in Eq. (39) are precisely the allowed “large gauge” labels of the clock phase convention; they are not an additional quantization postulate.

We define mismatch functionals

$$\delta_\theta := \oint_{\gamma_\theta} \mathcal{A} - 2\pi \left(N_\theta + \frac{\nu_\theta}{4} \right), \quad \delta_r := \oint_{\gamma_r} \mathcal{A} - 2\pi \left(N_r + \frac{\nu_r}{4} \right), \quad (40)$$

where $(N_\theta, N_r) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ and (ν_θ, ν_r) are universal defect indices (Section 6). Phase closure is the condition

$$\boxed{\delta_\theta = 0, \quad \delta_r = 0.} \quad (41)$$

Written out, this is

$$\boxed{\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A} = 2\pi N_i + \frac{\nu_i \pi}{2}, \quad i \in \{\theta, r\}.} \quad (42)$$

Up to the defect terms, Eq. (42) is exactly the EBK quantization rule [2]. Here it is not postulated: it is the statement that a transported clock phase closes on the fundamental cycles.

Finite linewidth and “approximate closure” The “strictly monochromatic” statement above is an idealization. Any concrete protected clock state has a finite clock linewidth Γ_0 (set by residual losses, noise, and finite observation time). In that case the operational requirement is not exact closure, but that no *resolved* sidebands fall within the protection window. In the shifted-comb description of Appendix A, the detunings of the near-line components are linear in the generator mismatches $(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$. Requiring the dominant detuned harmonics to satisfy $|\Delta\omega_{mn}| \lesssim \Gamma_0$ therefore translates into an action-dependent tolerance band $|\delta| \lesssim 2\pi \Gamma_0 / \Omega$ (schematically, with Ω a typical orbital frequency scale). Exact closure is the center of that band; Appendix A shows that (in the single-line protected regime) the excess near-line leakage grows quadratically as one moves away from it.

5.2. Why closure must hold on the torus generators

A natural question is why we impose closure on the two basic loops of the Kepler torus, rather than only requiring the phase to return after one ideal Kepler orbit. In the exactly integrable Coulomb/Kepler problem the motion is resonant ($\Omega_r = \Omega_\theta$), so an unperturbed orbit traces a *closed* curve on the torus. Requiring phase return only on that curve would constrain essentially one combination of actions (the principal action $J_r + J_\theta$), which is already enough to recover the Coulomb energy ladder.

But the regime of interest for a *protected* clock line is slightly less ideal. Any weak ingredient that makes the protected/unprotected distinction physically meaningful over long times—weak dissipation, weak stochastic forcing, or higher-order couplings beyond the retained truncation—also breaks the exact resonance and/or causes the slow angles to

wander. In a near-integrable situation with Ω_r/Ω_θ not exactly rational, the trajectory is quasi-periodic and explores the torus over long times rather than retracing one closed loop forever.

Example: a small degeneracy-breaking perturbation. To make the “torus wandering” statement concrete, start from the ideal Coulomb Hamiltonian $H_0(J_r, J_\theta) = H_{\text{Kep}}(J_r + J_\theta)$ and add a weak correction

$$H(J_r, J_\theta) = H_{\text{Kep}}(J_r + J_\theta) + \varepsilon H_1(J_r, J_\theta), \quad 0 < \varepsilon \ll 1, \quad (43)$$

where H_1 can represent (for example) a small relativistic correction, a finite-size/nonsingular core, or a weak external field treated in a secular/averaged way. The slow frequencies are

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_r &= \partial_{J_r} H = \Omega_0 + \varepsilon \partial_{J_r} H_1, \\ \Omega_\theta &= \partial_{J_\theta} H = \Omega_0 + \varepsilon \partial_{J_\theta} H_1, \\ \Omega_0 &:= \partial_{J_{\text{Kep}}} H_{\text{Kep}}. \end{aligned}$$

Unless H_1 depends only on $J_r + J_\theta$, the degeneracy is split at $O(\varepsilon)$:

$$\Omega_\theta - \Omega_r = \varepsilon (\partial_{J_\theta} - \partial_{J_r}) H_1 \neq 0 \quad (\text{generically}). \quad (44)$$

Then the motion on the torus is quasi-periodic, $\theta(t) = \Omega_\theta t + \theta_0$ and $\alpha_r(t) = \Omega_r t + \alpha_{r0}$, and the relative angle $\theta - \alpha_r$ precesses at rate $\Omega_\theta - \Omega_r$. Over a “precession time” $T_{\text{prec}} \sim 2\pi/|\Omega_\theta - \Omega_r|$ the trajectory winds around the torus rather than closing on a single diagonal loop. In that regime the defect-corrected clock factor is naturally a function on the torus, and any nonzero mismatch $(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$ produces the shifted near-line comb in Appendix A. Requiring closure only on the unperturbed diagonal Kepler orbit would not remove these sidebands once the degeneracy is split: what matters are the two independent generator mismatches that control quasi-periodic boundary conditions on \mathbb{T}^2 .

In that torus-wandering regime, “strictly monochromatic in the laboratory” is naturally a statement about a clock factor $U(\theta, \alpha_r)$ defined *on the torus*, not only along one special trajectory. A mismatch on either generator loop forces quasi-periodic boundary conditions for U and therefore shifted near-line spectral lines (Appendix A). With frequency-local protection, those detuned lines are generically unprotected and leak power. Thus generator closure is a natural *necessary* condition for long-lived monochromaticity in this regime. The phase-closure conditions in Eq. (41) are precisely the statement that the defect-corrected clock factor is single-valued on the torus (up to the universal defect slips).

6. Universal defect phases in the Coulomb problem

The phase-closure rule in Eq. (42) contains, besides the smooth transport 1-form \mathcal{A} , a pair of integers (ν_θ, ν_r) . They encode universal *phase slips* that appear when an oscillatory *return* object is continued through singular points of the slow Kepler motion. For the planar Coulomb problem those singular points are: (i) the two radial turning points and (ii) the polar coordinate singularity at $r = 0$.

These slips are not intrinsically “wave-only”. They appear whenever one transports an oscillatory phase variable through a singular reduction or coordinate chart and demands that a return quantity be continued consistently across that singularity. Turning points and the Coulomb center are precisely such singular loci for the reduced Kepler dynamics.

In our setting the oscillatory object is the internal clock envelope $\exp(-i\tilde{\phi})$ (equivalently, the defect-corrected U), and the slips are patching data for the clock’s transported phase on the torus. We therefore cite the standard Maslov/Langer literature, but interpret the slips as localized singular contributions to a transported *clock* phase rather than as caustic phases of a configuration-space wave.

In semiclassical mechanics the same slips are packaged as the Maslov index (turning points) and the Langer correction (the Coulomb origin) [3,4,9]. Here they enter for a different reason: in the protected narrowband regime the defect-corrected clock factor U is itself a return quantity, obtained by transporting a internal clock around cycles of the Kepler torus and projecting back onto the same clock mode. Near turning points and near $r = 0$, the continuation of such return objects is governed by universal stationary-phase normal forms. Appendix G records those normal forms; we quote only the resulting indices needed for the EBK lattice.

6.1. Turning points: the radial Maslov slip

A radial turning point is a *fold*: the local stationary-phase structure changes and a uniform approximation is required. The fold normal form is the Airy integral, which produces a fixed phase offset of $+\pi/2$ for each turning point (the Gouy/Maslov slip). A bound Kepler orbit has two turning points per radial cycle (periapsis and apoapsis), hence

$$\nu_r = 2. \tag{45}$$

6.2. Coulomb origin: the Langer half-shift

Although the slow orbit is planar, regularity at the Coulomb center is a three-dimensional requirement: the relevant return amplitude must be smooth in Cartesian coordinates at $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}$ before restricting to an orbital plane. Under a local second-order, rotationally invariant normal form for this amplitude (as in the dipole-order regulated return

map summarized in Appendix C), separation yields the standard centrifugal coefficient $\ell(\ell + 1)/r^2$ and a regular radial coordinate forces the replacement $\ell(\ell + 1) \mapsto (\ell + \frac{1}{2})^2$. In EBK language this is the Langer half-shift, i.e.

$$\nu_\theta = 2. \tag{46}$$

Putting the turning-point and origin slips together, planar Coulomb motion carries the defect pair

$$(\nu_r, \nu_\theta) = (2, 2). \tag{47}$$

Without these slips, phase closure would yield an integer lattice in units of $J_{\tau 0}$ (a pure Bohr–Sommerfeld rule). Including Eq. (47) produces the EBK half-shift lattice and hence the Coulomb principal offset $n = n_r + \ell + 1$.

7. Action lattice and the Coulomb energy ladder

7.1. The action lattice from the clock phase

The closure equations in Eq. (42) are, up to the defect slips, *mathematically identical* to the usual EBK rule (with \hbar replaced by $J_{\tau 0}$). We record the resulting planar lattice to make clear what is being closed: the slow phase of the internal clock, not a matter-wave phase.

Insert the leading proper-time 1-form of Eq. (33) into the closure condition in Eq. (42). The fundamental periods are

$$\oint_{\gamma_\theta} \mathcal{A}_\tau = 2\pi \frac{J_\theta}{J_{\tau 0}}, \quad \oint_{\gamma_r} \mathcal{A}_\tau = 2\pi \frac{J_r}{J_{\tau 0}}.$$

With $(\nu_r, \nu_\theta) = (2, 2)$, Eq. (42) gives the planar EBK lattice

$$\boxed{J_r = \left(n_r + \frac{1}{2}\right) J_{\tau 0}, \quad J_\theta = \left(\ell + \frac{1}{2}\right) J_{\tau 0}, \quad n_r, \ell \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}.} \tag{48}$$

The principal action in Eq. (15) becomes

$$\boxed{J_{\text{Kep}} = n J_{\tau 0}, \quad n := n_r + \ell + 1.} \tag{49}$$

7.2. The $1/n^2$ energy ladder in the action unit $J_{\tau 0}$

Because the Kepler Hamiltonian depends only on J_{Kep} , Eqs. (14) and (49) give immediately

$$\boxed{E_n = -\frac{\mu \kappa_C^2}{2n^2 J_{\tau 0}^2}.} \tag{50}$$

At this stage the spectrum is obtained in terms of the single action scale $J_{\tau 0} = 2\mu c^2/\omega_0$. Identifying $J_{\tau 0}$ with \hbar is a separate calibration step, discussed in Appendix B.

8. Why phase closure matters physically

Up to this point the action lattice has followed from closure of the slow clock phase. The remaining physical question is why a generator mismatch $(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$ should matter dynamically. The answer is spectral. The actual current contains the proper-time factor $e^{-i\omega_0\tau(t)}$, but radiation is emitted into Maxwell modes labeled by laboratory frequency. A return mismatch changes the slow envelope multiplying the protected lab-frequency line and therefore shifts spectral weight into *near-line sidebands*. Because protection is *frequency-local*, the clock line at ω_0 is canceled, but nearby detuned lines are generically unprotected and therefore leak power.

The intuition is the same as for a pure tone. A perfectly steady tone occupies one spectral line, while a slow modulation of that tone creates sidebands. Here the protected tone is the internal clock line. If the slow clock envelope does not close after the orbital returns, it is modulated on orbital time scales, and the spectrum is no longer concentrated at the protected line. The calculation below makes this statement local and quantitative: in the resolved narrowband regime, small detunings produce a quadratic excess leakage.

Near-integrable torus exploration and why generator phase returns matter In the ideal Kepler problem the two orbital frequencies are commensurate, so a single unperturbed ellipse is periodic and does not by itself wind both generators of \mathbb{T}^2 . The phase-closure conditions are nevertheless imposed on the generator loops because they control the phase accumulated under *any* slow excursion on the torus, and because any realistic completion of the model introduces small perturbations (post-Newtonian terms, finite-size operators, weak noise) that detune the Kepler degeneracy. During a long protected episode the slow angles then wind quasi-periodically and the clock envelope samples the torus. In this near-integrable sense, closure is a property of long-lived episodes near a given torus, not a statement about a single perfectly periodic Kepler ellipse.

Observable clock signal The relevant laboratory object is the radiating internal *bright* coordinate $q_+(t)$, or equivalently the corresponding effective dipole coefficient. Its microscopic phase is the proper-time phase of the clock. In the narrowband protected regime we express the same lab-time signal as a fast clock line at ω_0 times a slow envelope on the Kepler torus,

$$q_+(t) = \Re \left\{ Q_* e^{-i\omega_0 t} U(\theta(t), \alpha_r(t)) \right\}, \quad (51)$$

where Q_* is the nearly fixed clock amplitude and U is the defect-corrected clock factor defined in Section 5. The mismatch variables are invariant under slow rephasings $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi(\theta, \alpha_r)$, so they cannot be removed by a phase convention.

Figure 1. Schematic frequency picture behind the “selection” logic. The protected clock-line root cancels the electric-parity dipole coefficient at ω_0 , but only locally in frequency. A closed slow envelope keeps the dominant clock component pinned to this protected line. A non-closing envelope is a slow modulation of the clock signal, and modulation creates a near-line comb (Eq. (52)). Phase mismatch shifts the comb; in particular it detunes the dominant $(m, n) = (0, 0)$ line with magnitude $|\Delta\omega_{00}| = |\Omega_\theta\delta_\theta + \Omega_r\delta_r|/2\pi$. If $\Gamma_0 \lesssim \Omega$ the detuning is resolved, and frequency-local protection implies a quadratic radiative penalty in $\Delta\omega$ for each line.

Mismatch \Rightarrow shifted near-line components Phase mismatch enforces quasi-periodic boundary conditions for U on the torus generators; equivalently the Fourier indices are shifted by $\beta_\theta := -\delta_\theta/2\pi$ and $\beta_r := -\delta_r/2\pi$. As a result the laboratory spectrum contains a shifted near-line comb

$$\omega_{mn} = \omega_0 + (m + \beta_\theta)\Omega_\theta + (n + \beta_r)\Omega_r, \quad (m, n \in \mathbb{Z}), \quad (52)$$

derived explicitly in Appendix A.

Frequency-local protection \Rightarrow quadratic detuning law, and a near-closure excess penalty At retained dipole order the radiated power in a monochromatic line ω may be written (e.g. [12])

$$\langle P_\infty \rangle(\omega) = \frac{\omega^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} |\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega)|^2. \quad (53)$$

On the protected internal mode the electric-type dipole coefficient satisfies $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}$. Generically the zero is simple, $\partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}|_{\omega_0} \neq 0$, so a detuned line at $\omega_0 + \Delta$ radiates with power $O(\Delta^2)$. Combining this Taylor law with the detunings in Eq. (52) shows that *each* near-line component carries power quadratic in its detuning. To turn the per-line law into a statement about total near-line leakage, we distinguish baseline leakage at phase closure from mismatch-induced *excess* leakage:

$$P_{\text{ex}}(\delta_\theta, \delta_r) := P_{\text{leak}}(\delta_\theta, \delta_r) - P_{\text{leak}}(0, 0). \quad (54)$$

In the single-line protected regime (i.e. when the constant mode $(m, n) = (0, 0)$ dominates the near-line content of U), the excess is dominated by the detuned $(0, 0)$ line, giving the

nonnegative rank-one quadratic contribution

$$P_{\text{ex}}^{(00)} \propto (\Omega_\theta \delta_\theta + \Omega_r \delta_r)^2 \quad (\text{explicitly, Eq. (70) in Appendix A}). \quad (55)$$

This is a quadratic leakage penalty for the resolved dominant detuning. A positive-definite penalty in the two independent mismatch variables would require additional independent near-line components, weak degeneracy-breaking, or a fuller kinetic model.

Why monochromaticity is plausible The “single-line” hypothesis is not automatic: periodicity of $U(\theta, \alpha_r)$ does not by itself force U to be constant. However, within the protected-line picture there is a simple dynamical reason to expect that a *long-lived* protected episode will become close to monochromatic. Expand the defect-corrected clock factor in its quasi-periodic Fourier series,

$$U(\theta, \alpha_r) = \sum_{m,n \in \mathbb{Z}} U_{mn} e^{i[(m+\beta_\theta)\theta + (n+\beta_r)\alpha_r]},$$

so that each coefficient produces a laboratory line at ω_{mn} (Eq. (52)). Within the locality window, the leaked power in that line is quadratic both in the coefficient and in the detuning, $P_{mn} \propto |U_{mn}|^2 \Delta\omega_{mn}^2$ (Appendix A). For a linear line oscillator, radiated power translates directly into decay of the corresponding harmonic energy, so the *damping rate* of that harmonic is also proportional to $\Delta\omega_{mn}^2$. This mode-by-mode damping picture is intended as an effective *linear, narrowband* argument; strong cross-mode coupling or nonlinear redistribution of spectral weight is not modeled here.

Detuned harmonics therefore damp faster than the least-detuned one. Over a protected episode lasting many damping times of the detuned harmonics, the envelope is driven toward the least-leaky harmonic. At exact phase closure the least-detuned harmonic is the constant mode $(m, n) = (0, 0)$, so the long-lived protected signal is expected to become dominated by that mode. This provides a mechanism-level motivation for the regime in which Eq. (55) governs the *excess* leakage, without claiming a complete kinetics for the actions (J_r, J_θ) .

Energetic interpretation (what is claimed, and what is not) The mechanism-level claim is narrow. This section establishes a local leakage cost for phase mismatch; it does not derive a complete kinetic relaxation law for the orbital actions. Within a long-lived protected-clock episode in which the near-line comb is resolved ($\Gamma_0 \lesssim \Omega$) and radiative damping has driven the envelope toward a single least-leaky near-line harmonic (the “single-line” limit motivated above), the mismatch-induced *excess* near-line leakage contains the nonnegative quadratic contribution of Eq. (55). For the dominant $(0, 0)$ line this quadratic is rank-one in $(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$, so it should not be read as a complete positive-definite selection potential on the two-action space.

In words: closure pins the dominant clock line to the protected frequency ω_0 ; a mismatch detunes that line by $\Delta\omega_{00}$ and opens a radiative channel whose power rises quadratically in that detuning. Independent sideband components or weak degeneracy-breaking can add further quadratic directions, but a full two-dimensional attractor is beyond the present calculation.

This does *not* by itself supply a full kinetic attractor for the orbital actions. A minimal dynamical setting in which such a penalty can bias state occupancy is an open system with slow drift of the actions (noise, weak dissipation) punctuated by long-lived protected-clock intervals; during each protected interval, excess near-line leakage produces an additional state-dependent energy-loss rate that disfavors mismatched tori. In the simplest toy picture one can model the slow evolution as diffusion/drift on action space together with a mismatch-dependent sink (or drift) proportional to $P_{\text{ex}}(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$; the resulting stationary measure is then biased toward closure. A full derivation would require specifying and controlling that nonequilibrium kinetics (for example, a Fokker–Planck equation for the distribution on (J_r, J_θ) with leakage-dependent coefficients), as well as controlling orbital-band stability; both are outside scope.

9. Interpretation and limitations

9.1. Angular action versus mechanical orbital angular momentum

Eq. (48) quantizes the *angular action* J_θ that appears in the phase-closure integrals. In a smooth central problem one may identify J_θ with the mechanical invariant $L := |\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{p}|$. In Coulomb, however, regularity at the $r = 0$ coordinate singularity forces the Langer defect (Subsection 6.2, Eqs. (108)–(109)), so the separation constant controlling the $1/r^2$ barrier is $\ell(\ell + 1)$ even though the EBK action is $J_\theta = (\ell + \frac{1}{2})J_{\tau 0}$. A convenient bookkeeping identity is therefore

$$L^2 := J_{\tau 0}^2 \ell(\ell + 1) = J_{\tau 0}^2 \left[\left(\ell + \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{4} \right] = J_\theta^2 - \frac{J_{\tau 0}^2}{4}. \quad (56)$$

In particular, for $\ell = 0$ one has $J_\theta = J_{\tau 0}/2$ but $L = 0$: the half-unit in J_θ is a universal defect contribution (Langer), not a nonzero mechanical orbital angular momentum.

9.2. Other limitations

- **Stability of matter and orbital-band radiation (the classical obstruction):** the present dipole-truncated construction does not resolve the stability-of-matter problem for a Maxwell-based atom: in bare Maxwell–Lorentz an accelerated charge radiates strongly at orbital frequencies. Internal protection at ω_0 is used here only as a premise for a *near-line* leakage penalty; we do not suppress orbital-band radiation.

For orientation, a nonrelativistic charge in a circular orbit of radius r and speed v radiates (Larmor) power

$$P_{\text{orb}} = \frac{e^2 a^2}{6\pi\epsilon_0 c^3}, \quad a = \frac{v^2}{r}.$$

At Bohr scales ($r \sim a_0$ and $v \sim \alpha c$) this gives $P_{\text{orb}} \sim 5 \times 10^{-8}$ W, while the binding energy is $|E| \sim 13.6$ eV $\simeq 2.2 \times 10^{-18}$ J, corresponding to a classical decay time $|E|/P_{\text{orb}} \sim 5 \times 10^{-11}$ s. This well-known estimate shows that, in bare Maxwell–Lorentz, orbital-band losses dominate.

Accordingly, the phase-closure mechanism should be read as *conditional*: it addresses which Kepler tori are compatible with a long-lived protected internal clock line *if* some additional physics (outside this paper) makes the slow Kepler torus a meaningful long-time state. Under that condition, phase closure selects an EBK lattice of such tori. For background on radiation reaction and self-force issues in classical electrodynamics, see e.g. [22–26].

- **Beyond leading order:** higher-order terms modify \mathcal{A} and the slow dynamics but do not remove the basic loop-integral structure (a loop integral of a 1-form).
- **Calibration:** the clock-closure argument produces an EBK lattice in the unit $J_{\tau 0}$. Identifying $J_{\tau 0}$ with \hbar requires either empirical calibration or additional modeling (Appendix B).
- **Planar scope and 3D extension:** the main derivation is carried out for planar orbits (sufficient for the n^{-2} ladder because Coulomb energy depends only on the principal action). For the natural extension to the full 3D Kepler torus, see Subsection 9.3.
- **Kinetics:** we give an explicit spectral/scaling leakage result (Section 8 and Appendix A), but we do not derive from first principles a full stochastic evolution leading to state populations.

9.3. 3D Kepler: expected extension

The main derivation is carried out for planar Kepler motion. This is enough to recover the Coulomb n^{-2} ladder because the Kepler energy depends only on the principal action.

A full 3D Kepler problem is also integrable, but its invariant manifold is a three-torus with three angles and three actions. If the same lab-time envelope construction extends in the same way, then at leading order one expects a transport 1-form on \mathbb{T}^3 of the form

$$\mathcal{A}_\tau = \frac{J_1}{J_{\tau 0}} d\vartheta^1 + \frac{J_2}{J_{\tau 0}} d\vartheta^2 + \frac{J_3}{J_{\tau 0}} d\vartheta^3,$$

so the same closure logic would quantize all three actions in the *same* unit $J_{\tau 0}$.

Because Coulomb energy depends only on the principal Kepler action (a sum of the actions), the n^{-2} ladder would persist, while the additional closures would encode the angular degeneracy structure (including an m -type quantum number). In standard Delaunay-type actions one may take $J_\phi = L_z$, $J_\theta = L - L_z$, and $J_r = J_{\text{Kep}} - L$, so that $J_{\text{Kep}} = J_r + J_\theta + J_\phi$ before singular patching. If the proper-time transport extends to \mathbb{T}^3 as $\mathcal{A}_\tau = \sum_i (J_i/J_{\tau 0}) d\vartheta^i$, then generator closure would quantize these actions in the same unit $J_{\tau 0}$. The relation between the quantized angular actions and the mechanical angular-momentum separation constants must then be fixed by the corresponding Langer-type defect bookkeeping; in the planar reduction used here this bookkeeping is Eq. (56), not the naive identification $L = J_\theta$.

Working out the defect indices and frequency-protection physics in 3D is left for future work.

9.4. A falsifiable beyond-ladder consequence: the expected correction scale Define the dimensionless Coulomb strength in the action unit $J_{\tau 0}$ by

$$\alpha_\tau := \frac{\kappa_C}{c J_{\tau 0}},$$

which coincides with the usual fine-structure constant if the external calibration $J_{\tau 0} = \hbar$ is adopted. On a Coulomb torus with principal action $J_{\text{Kep}} \sim n J_{\tau 0}$, the orbital speed scales as $v/c \sim \kappa_C/(c J_{\text{Kep}}) \sim \alpha_\tau/n$. The next proper-time term (and likewise generic relativistic corrections in $\delta\mathcal{A}$ or in H_{Kep}) therefore shifts generator phase returns by a relative amount $O((\alpha_\tau/n)^2)$. Consequently, any controlled completion of the model that preserves the proper-time one-form predicts leading energy corrections at the scale

$$\delta E \sim \mu c^2 \frac{\alpha_\tau^4}{n^4},$$

with the detailed (n, ℓ) dependence set by the specific correction retained (e.g. post-Newtonian Kepler terms, additional Maxwell–Lorentz dressing contributions collected in $\delta\mathcal{A}$, etc.).

10. Conclusion

The mechanism uses one physical clock: the internal clock phase $\phi = \omega_0 \tau$. Laboratory time t enters because radiation is organized by lab-frame frequency. Factoring the actual source $e^{-i\omega_0 \tau(t)}$ as a laboratory clock line $e^{-i\omega_0 t}$ times a slow envelope $e^{-i\omega_0(\tau-t)}$ exposes the lab-time spectrum of the same current. It is not a comparison between two independent clocks. For slow Kepler motion this envelope phase is proportional to the mechanical action one-form on the torus.

In a long-lived narrowband clock regime—supplied here by an effective Maxwell–Lorentz clock interface plus a stable-clock assumption—“globally

monochromatic in the laboratory” is naturally a statement about this slow clock envelope on the Kepler torus. If the proper-time transport dominates the closed-loop periods, then requiring the defect-corrected clock envelope to be single-valued on the radial and angular returns gives the planar EBK half-shift lattice in the single action unit $J_{\tau 0}$, and therefore the Coulomb n^{-2} ladder.

A separate spectral calculation shows why this closure condition has physical force in the model. A small return mismatch shifts part of the clock signal into nearby sidebands. Because the long-lived line is protected only locally in frequency, those sidebands leak. Near closure the leakage is quadratic in the resolved detuning. This does not by itself provide a full kinetic selection theory, but it gives a concrete radiative cost for the same phase mismatch that EBK removes.

The action unit is $J_{\tau 0} = 2\mu c^2/\omega_0$. Matching $J_{\tau 0}$ to \hbar is treated as an external empirical/interface calibration (Appendix B), not as part of the phase-closure derivation.

Interpretive remark: phase without a matter wave At the level of semiclassical quantization, the indispensable ingredient is a phase that accumulates consistently on the fundamental cycles of an invariant torus. In wave mechanics that phase is commonly attributed to a configuration-space wave and quantization is phrased as single-valuedness of a wave factor. Here the same closure mathematics attaches instead to the lab-time envelope phase of a localized internal clock whose underlying phase advances in proper time.

As emphasized in the Scope statement (Subsection 1.5) and in the limitations discussion (Section 9), the present paper does not address orbital-band stability, interference amplitudes, tunneling rates, or measurement statistics. Its implication is narrower but conceptually sharp: EBK closure can be understood as global coherence of the lab-time envelope of an internal proper-time clock, with frequency-local radiative leakage supplying a concrete cost for detuning resolved near-line components.

Outlook: scope beyond the Coulomb problem The leading geometric step of the mechanism is not specific to the Kepler potential. Whenever the orbital sector is an integrable nonrelativistic system with standard kinetic energy and no vector potential at leading order, so that $p = \mu\dot{q}$ and hence $p \cdot dq = \mu v^2 dt$ (cf. Eq. (27)), the lab-time envelope of the proper-time clock induces a phase-transport 1-form whose generator periods are proportional to the actions on the invariant torus: $p \cdot dq = \sum_i J_i d\theta_i + dF$ implies $\mathcal{A}_\tau = \sum_i (J_i/J_{\tau 0}) d\theta_i$ up to a gauge. Thus phase closure reproduces the EBK action lattice (with the appropriate Maslov indices of the given torus) in the single action unit $J_{\tau 0} = 2\mu c^2/\omega_0$.

The Coulomb problem is special mainly in that its defect indices can be made fully explicit (turning-point and origin/Langer slips) and the resulting closure immediately yields the n^{-2} ladder. The leakage-based enforcement of closure is expected to extend to general

integrable tori provided the internal clock line exhibits frequency-local protection at ω_0 and the long-lived regime is dominated by one near-line component in the sense defined in Sec. 8, so that phase mismatch generically shifts near-line spectral weight onto detuned, unprotected sidebands. Whether weak dissipation can dynamically relax all relevant action combinations toward the nearest closure lattice point in a multi-action system is an open dynamical question left for future work.

A separate caveat concerns *vector potentials*. In the presence of electromagnetic gauge fields the canonical 1-form is no longer purely mechanical: for a particle of charge q_{ch} one has $\boldsymbol{\pi} = \mu\dot{\mathbf{r}} + q_{\text{ch}}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r})$ and hence $\boldsymbol{\pi} \cdot d\mathbf{r} = \mu v^2 dt + q_{\text{ch}}\mathbf{A} \cdot d\mathbf{r}$. Proper-time slip accounts only for the v^2 term, so reproducing the full EBK periods in such settings would require an *additional* phase-transport contribution beyond proper time. A natural guess is that the same internal clock phase is also transported by the electromagnetic gauge potential, so that, in addition to \mathcal{A}_τ , one has a term

$$\boxed{\mathcal{A}_{\text{em}} = \frac{q_{\text{ch}}}{J_{\tau 0}} \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}) \cdot d\mathbf{r}, \quad \Delta\tilde{\phi}(\gamma) = - \oint_{\gamma} (\mathcal{A}_\tau + \mathcal{A}_{\text{em}}) + \dots} \quad (57)$$

Its generator periods are not tied to v/c and can therefore be order unity even when the orbital motion is nonrelativistic. Unlike the metric/time-dilation contribution, Eq. (57) would be fixed not by kinematics but by electromagnetic gauge invariance: if the clock factor is a charged phase variable, then the unique local worldline coupling linear in the potentials that produces a gauge-invariant integral on closed loops is $q_{\text{ch}} \int A_\mu dx^\mu$. Dividing by the same action unit $J_{\tau 0}$ converts this contribution into a dimensionless phase increment. Developing this extension (and its relation to the $\delta\mathcal{A}$ split in Sec. 4.2) is left to future work.

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Supplementary information No separate Supplementary Information is required; the appendices include the Maxwell–Lorentz clock-interface material used by the main text.

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Note on the appendices The main text is organized so that the logical dependencies are visible. The appendices provide the self-contained technical material behind the protected internal-clock premise, the leakage estimate, subleading drift estimates, and the defect slips. They are not required to follow the internal-clock \Rightarrow EBK \Rightarrow n^{-2} ladder chain, but they record exactly what is being assumed and what is derived at the Maxwell–Lorentz interface.

A. Closed-loop mismatch and quadratic leakage

This appendix supplies a concrete link between (i) a small phase mismatch $(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$ on the Kepler torus and (ii) nonzero radiated power from *near-line* spectral lines in the protected internal clock state. The two inputs are simple: (a) mismatch enforces quasi-periodic boundary conditions for the clock factor on the slow torus, and (b) protection is frequency-local: $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}$ but generically $\partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}|_{\omega_0} \neq 0$.

A.1. Quasi-periodic boundary conditions from closed-loop mismatch

Recall the demodulated phase $\tilde{\phi}$ defined in Eq. (36). It is the slow lab-time envelope phase of the actual proper-time current, obtained after factoring out the protected clock line: $\dot{\tilde{\phi}}(t) = -\mathcal{A}(\dot{\gamma})$. Across a generator loop γ_i the smooth transport gives the geometric phase $\Delta\tilde{\phi}(\gamma_i) = -\oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}$ (Eq. (19)). At caustics one must include the universal defect slips (Section 6), which contribute $+\nu_i\pi/2$ to the fast return phase on generator $i \in \{\theta, r\}$. Define the *defect-corrected clock factor*

$$U(\theta, \alpha_r) := \exp\left(-i\tilde{\phi}(\theta, \alpha_r)\right) \exp\left(-i\frac{\nu_\theta}{4}\theta - i\frac{\nu_r}{4}\alpha_r\right). \tag{58}$$

Traversing γ_θ (advance $\theta \mapsto \theta + 2\pi$ at fixed α_r) multiplies U by $\exp(+i\delta_\theta)$, and similarly for γ_r . Equivalently, U obeys the quasi-periodic boundary conditions

$$U(\theta + 2\pi, \alpha_r) = e^{+i\delta_\theta} U(\theta, \alpha_r), \quad U(\theta, \alpha_r + 2\pi) = e^{+i\delta_r} U(\theta, \alpha_r), \tag{59}$$

where $(\delta_\theta, \delta_r)$ are the mismatch functionals in Eq. (40). Phase closure is $\delta_\theta = \delta_r = 0$, in which case U is single-valued (periodic) on the torus.

A.2. A shifted Fourier comb in laboratory time

This is where the demodulation becomes operational. Maxwell radiation modes are labeled by the laboratory time t , so the emitted near-line spectrum is obtained by Fourier decomposing the lab-time signal $e^{-i\omega_0 t} U(\theta(t), \alpha_r(t))$.

Introduce dimensionless mismatch angles

$$\beta_\theta := -\frac{\delta_\theta}{2\pi}, \quad \beta_r := -\frac{\delta_r}{2\pi}, \tag{60}$$

and define the strictly periodic function

$$\bar{U}(\theta, \alpha_r) := e^{i(\beta_\theta\theta + \beta_r\alpha_r)} U(\theta, \alpha_r).$$

By construction, \bar{U} is 2π -periodic in both θ and α_r , so it has a double Fourier expansion

$$\bar{U}(\theta, \alpha_r) = \sum_{m,n \in \mathbb{Z}} \bar{U}_{mn} e^{-i(m\theta + n\alpha_r)}. \tag{61}$$

Undoing the definition of \bar{U} yields the *shifted* (quasi-periodic) expansion

$$U(\theta, \alpha_r) = \sum_{m,n \in \mathbb{Z}} \bar{U}_{mn} e^{-i[(m+\beta_\theta)\theta + (n+\beta_r)\alpha_r]}. \tag{62}$$

Along a fixed Kepler torus, the slow angles advance linearly, $\theta(t) = \Omega_\theta t + \theta_0$ and $\alpha_r(t) = \Omega_r t + \alpha_{r0}$, so Eq. (62) becomes a discrete time-frequency comb:

$$U(t) = \sum_{m,n \in \mathbb{Z}} \tilde{U}_{mn} e^{-i\Delta\omega_{mn}t}, \quad \Delta\omega_{mn} := (m + \beta_\theta)\Omega_\theta + (n + \beta_r)\Omega_r, \tag{63}$$

with $\tilde{U}_{mn} := \bar{U}_{mn} e^{-i(m\theta_0 + n\alpha_{r0})}$.

The key point is that we did *not* assume any particular time-domain modulation. The shifted comb in Eq. (63) is forced by the quasi-periodic boundary conditions in Eq. (59).

A.3. Frequency-local protection gives quadratic leakage near closure

Write the bright clock coordinate in narrowband form

$$q_+(t) = \Re\left\{ Q_* e^{-i\omega_0 t} U(t) \right\}, \tag{64}$$

where Q_* is the nearly fixed clock amplitude (set by the ZPF-nearly fixed action, or treated empirically as a constant in the present paper). Using Eq. (63), q_+ has discrete spectral lines at

$$\omega_{mn} = \omega_0 + \Delta\omega_{mn}. \tag{65}$$

At retained (dipole) order, the radiated power of a monochromatic line is

$$P_\infty(\omega) = \frac{\omega^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} |\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega)|^2,$$

and for the internal mode we write the radiating coefficient as $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega)$. A spectral line of q_+ with complex amplitude $Q_{mn} := Q_* \tilde{U}_{mn}$ contributes an effective dipole line $Q_{mn} \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_{mn})$. Therefore, restricting attention to the *near-line* lines for which frequency-local protection is the right approximation, we proceed as follows. Fix a locality window Δ_{loc} (for example Eq. (11)) and define the near-line index set

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{loc}} := \left\{ (m, n) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 : |\Delta\omega_{mn}| \leq \Delta_{\text{loc}} \right\}. \tag{66}$$

(Equivalently, we restrict to those lines within Δ_{loc} of ω_0 .) The leaked power carried by this near-line set is

$$P_{\text{leak}} = \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{loc}}} \frac{\omega_{mn}^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} |Q_{mn}|^2 |\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_{mn})|^2. \tag{67}$$

For simplicity this is written as a non-degenerate sum over lines. If several pairs (m, n) share the same ω_{mn} , one should group by distinct frequencies and sum the complex amplitudes coherently; this changes coefficients but not the near-closure scaling discussed below.

Dynamic protection is the clock-line condition

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}.$$

Because this cancellation is frequency-local, for detunings $|\Delta| \leq \Delta_{\text{loc}}$ we may Taylor expand

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0 + \Delta) = \Delta \partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}|_{\omega_0} + O(\Delta^2). \tag{68}$$

Insert Eq. (68) and $\omega_{mn} \simeq \omega_0$ into Eq. (67). To leading order,

$$P_{\text{leak}} \simeq \frac{\omega_0^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} \left| \partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}|_{\omega_0} \right|^2 \sum_{(m,n) \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{loc}}} |Q_{mn}|^2 \Delta \omega_{mn}^2. \tag{69}$$

What is rigorous, and what is a model assumption. Up to Eq. (69) the reasoning is purely kinematic: mismatch fixes *where* the lines are (a shifted comb), and frequency-local protection fixes that each line’s radiated power is quadratic in its detuning $\Delta\omega_{mn}$. To connect the per-line quadratic detuning law to a statement about *total* near-line leakage, one must say something about the Fourier weights $|Q_{mn}|^2$. The point is that phase closure ($\delta_\theta = \delta_r = 0$) enforces periodic boundary conditions, but periodicity alone does not force the clock factor to be constant; a periodic U may already carry sidebands at $\omega_0 + m\Omega_\theta + n\Omega_r$. Accordingly, it is often cleaner to discuss a *mismatch-induced excess* leakage,

$$P_{\text{ex}} := P_{\text{leak}}(\delta_\theta, \delta_r) - P_{\text{leak}}(0, 0),$$

and then ask under what dynamical conditions P_{ex} is dominated by the detuned $(m, n) = (0, 0)$ line.

To obtain the near-closure scaling quoted in the main text we use a *clock history smoothness* hypothesis: in the long-lived protected regime, the clock factor is close to constant on the torus when $\delta_\theta = \delta_r = 0$, so that the central coefficient dominates and the off-central Fourier weights are small. This is the dynamical input that says the protected clock signal is nearly monochromatic.”

Near such a clock history, the nearest line is $(m, n) = (0, 0)$ with $\Delta\omega_{00} = \beta_\theta\Omega_\theta + \beta_r\Omega_r = -(\Omega_\theta\delta_\theta + \Omega_r\delta_r)/(2\pi)$, so its contribution is

$$P_{\text{leak}}^{(00)} \simeq \frac{\omega_0^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0c^3} |Q_*|^2 \left| \partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})} \Big|_{\omega_0} \right|^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_\theta \delta_\theta + \Omega_r \delta_r}{2\pi} \right)^2, \quad (70)$$

which is nonnegative and quadratic in the resolved detuning. It is, however, a rank-one quadratic form in the two mismatch variables. It therefore supplies a leakage penalty for the combination $\Omega_\theta\delta_\theta + \Omega_r\delta_r$, not by itself a positive-definite penalty in both independent generator mismatches. A strictly positive-definite two-generator penalty would require adding other independent near-line components, weak degeneracy-breaking, or a specified kinetic model for how spectral weight is redistributed among nearby lines. In the clock history-monochromatic regime one has $P_{\text{leak}}^{(00)} \approx P_{\text{ex}}$ for this dominant resolved line.

Remark on Kepler degeneracy. For the ideal Kepler problem one has $\Omega_\theta = \Omega_r$, so many integer pairs (m, n) share the same $\Delta\omega_{mn}$. In practice any small symmetry-breaking perturbation (relativistic corrections, weak external fields, higher-order terms beyond the truncation) splits this degeneracy. The shifted-comb conclusion and the quadratic detuning law remain; only the bookkeeping of coincident lines changes. If the degeneracy is kept, one should group the coincident frequencies and sum the complex amplitudes coherently before squaring; this changes coefficients but not the $O(\delta_\theta^2 + \delta_r^2)$ scaling near closure.

B. Fixing the action unit J_{τ_0} (external calibration)

The geometric phase-closure steps of the main text yield quantization in the single action unit J_{τ_0} defined in Eq. (32). To express results in conventional units one must fix that unit. We keep that step logically separate from the phase-closure argument.

B.1. Empirical calibration (minimal, experiment-first)

One may simply treat J_{τ_0} as an empirical constant. Then Eq. (50) is the prediction, and matching one spectral line fixes J_{τ_0} . Nothing in the geometric argument depends on *how* the unit is fixed.

B.2. A ZPF/SED route (model-dependent bookkeeping)

In stochastic electrodynamics, the universal normalization of the zero-point field fixes the stationary energy of a harmonic oscillator to $\langle E \rangle = \frac{1}{2}\hbar\omega$ (see, e.g., [14–16]). In the action convention $H = \omega J$ this corresponds to the stationary action

$$J_{\text{ZPF}} = \hbar/2.$$

In the present reduced model the internal clock is a narrowband oscillator sustained (in the protected regime) at a nearly fixed action $J_+^* \simeq J_{\text{ZPF}}$.

To relate this calibrated clock scale to the proper-time action unit $J_{\tau 0} = 2\mu c^2/\omega_0$ one must specify how the effective Kepler inertial parameter μ is partitioned between (i) the energy stored in the *clocked* internal mode and (ii) all other contributions to the inertia of the reduced dressed system. For Coulomb/hydrogen, μ is the usual reduced mass of the relative coordinate (numerically $\mu \simeq m_e$), but the bookkeeping below does not attribute the nuclear rest mass to the clock; it pertains only to the effective inertia appearing in the reduced Kepler sector.

A concise way to represent this partition is the worldline action (written in reparametrization-invariant form)

$$S_{\text{wl}} = \int \left(- [\mu_{\text{nc}}c^2 + H_{\text{int}}(J_+)] d\tau \right), \tag{71}$$

where $H_{\text{int}}(J_+)$ is the Hamiltonian of the *clocked* internal mode and μ_{nc} collects the remaining “non-clock” contribution to the Kepler inertial parameter. In a point-particle Maxwell–Lorentz model without an explicit internal sector, this μ_{nc} is precisely the renormalized mass parameter inserted by hand after integrating out (and regularizing) the near-zone self-field. Here part of the near-zone dynamics is retained explicitly, so it is natural to keep the split visible.

Expanding $d\tau = dt\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = dt(1 - \frac{v^2}{2c^2} + \dots)$ shows that internal energy contributes to inertia:

$$\mu = \mu_{\text{nc}} + \frac{\langle H_{\text{int}} \rangle}{c^2}. \tag{72}$$

Here μ_{nc} may include (for example) a bare core term, static near-zone field energy, additional internal/dark modes, or any other dressing not captured by the single clocked action J_+ ; only the energy on the clocked mode $H_{\text{int}}(J_+)$ contributes to $\omega_0 = \partial H_{\text{int}}/\partial J_+$.

Equating $\langle H_{\text{int}} \rangle = (\mu - \mu_{\text{nc}})c^2$ from Eq. (72) with $\langle H_{\text{int}} \rangle \simeq \omega_0(\hbar/2)$ gives $\omega_0 \simeq 2(\mu - \mu_{\text{nc}})c^2/\hbar$, hence

$$J_{\tau 0} = \frac{2\mu c^2}{\omega_0} = \frac{\mu}{\mu - \mu_{\text{nc}}} \hbar. \tag{73}$$

It is convenient to introduce the “clock fraction”

$$\eta := \frac{\mu - \mu_{\text{nc}}}{\mu} \in (0, 1], \quad \text{so that} \quad J_{\tau 0} = \frac{\hbar}{\eta}.$$

Thus $J_{\tau 0} = \hbar$ corresponds to the idealized interface limit $\eta = 1$ (equivalently $\mu_{\text{nc}} = 0$), in which the effective Kepler inertia is dominated by the clocked internal energy. In general one expects $\eta < 1$, so $J_{\tau 0} > \hbar$ even if a ZPF argument pins $J_+^* = \hbar/2$ for the clock mode. For that reason we do *not* treat any particular value of η (or of μ_{nc}) as a conclusion of this paper: $J_{\tau 0}$ remains an empirically calibrated action unit unless additional physics fixes the mass split.

We emphasize that this is an *interface identification* (one datum), not part of the phase-closure geometry. The EBK lattice and the spectrum in Eq. (50) follow from closure in units of $J_{\tau 0}$ regardless of how $J_{\tau 0}$ is fixed.

C. Regulated Maxwell–Lorentz clock interface: $E1 \oplus T1$, one bright mode, and the anapole root

This appendix records the clock interface used in the main text in a self-contained form. As emphasized in Section 1.2, the goal is not to derive a finite near-zone electron model from a bare point charge. The finite source is an effective near-zone interface for the unresolved charge-plus-field dressing. The starting point is therefore a regulated, Lorentz-covariant extended-source model: the charge has finite support of size R and its current is decomposed as

$$J^\mu = J_{\text{free}}^\mu + J_{\text{b}}^\mu, \tag{74}$$

where J_{free}^μ is the transported charge current and J_{b}^μ is a localized neutral internal current supported in the same near-zone region. The existence of this internal current sector is the effective-model input. Rest-frame profiles such as $\delta_R(\mathbf{x})$ below are understood as spatial profiles on the instantaneous hypersurface orthogonal to the worldline, transported with the source; the displayed rest-frame formulas are the local representation of this covariant finite-source description. What is derived below is the leading Maxwell–Lorentz near-zone dynamics of that sector, its protected electric-parity clock line, and its proper-time phase law.

C.1. Field elimination and the PV/light-shell split

In the instantaneous rest frame of the finite source, eliminating the electromagnetic field gives a quadratic functional of the internal current. For the transverse vector part and the Coulomb part one may write schematically

$$S_{\text{bb}} = -\frac{1}{2\epsilon_0} \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{b}}(\omega, \mathbf{k}) \tilde{\rho}_{\text{b}}(-\omega, -\mathbf{k})}{k^2} + \frac{\mu_0}{2} \int \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{\tilde{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{b}}^*(\omega, \mathbf{k}) \cdot \mathbf{P}_T(\hat{\mathbf{k}}) \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_{\text{b}}(\omega, \mathbf{k})}{k^2 - \omega^2/c^2 - i0 \operatorname{sgn}(\omega)}. \tag{75}$$

Here $\mathbf{P}_T(\hat{\mathbf{k}}) = I - \hat{\mathbf{k}}\hat{\mathbf{k}}^T$ is the transverse projector. The denominator splits into a real principal-value (PV) part and an on-shell light-shell part,

$$\frac{1}{x - i0 \operatorname{sgn}(\omega)} = \operatorname{PV}\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + i\pi \operatorname{sgn}(\omega)\delta(x). \tag{76}$$

The PV part is reactive and gives the local conservative internal Lagrangian after a low-frequency expansion and renormalization. The delta-function part is radiative: it samples only $k = |\omega|/c$ and therefore only the outgoing light-shell amplitudes.

C.2. Localized $E1 \oplus T1$ current basis

Let $\delta_R(\mathbf{x})$ be a smooth isotropic regulator supported on the source scale R and normalized to unit integral. The retained electric-parity $l = 1$ sector is represented by two localized currents. The electric dipole channel is a localized polarization,

$$\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{d}(t)\delta_R(\mathbf{x}), \quad \rho_E = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{P}, \quad \mathbf{J}_E = \partial_t \mathbf{P}, \quad (77)$$

which is conserved by construction. The toroidal electric-parity channel is a localized solenoidal double-curl current,

$$\mathbf{J}_Q(\mathbf{x}, t) = \nabla \times \nabla \times (\mathbf{Q}(t)\delta_R(\mathbf{x})), \quad \rho_Q \equiv 0, \quad (78)$$

so $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_Q \equiv 0$. In Fourier space, evaluated in the co-moving frame,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{J}}_E = -i\omega \mathbf{d}(\omega)\tilde{\delta}_R(\mathbf{k}), \quad \tilde{\rho}_E = -i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{d}(\omega)\tilde{\delta}_R(\mathbf{k}), \quad (79)$$

while

$$\tilde{\mathbf{J}}_Q = k^2 P_T(\hat{\mathbf{k}})\mathbf{Q}(\omega)\tilde{\delta}_R(\mathbf{k}). \quad (80)$$

Thus the transverse internal current factorizes as

$$\boxed{P_T \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_b = \tilde{\delta}_R(\mathbf{k}) P_T(\hat{\mathbf{k}}) \left[-i\omega \mathbf{d}(\omega) + k^2 \mathbf{Q}(\omega) \right]}. \quad (81)$$

This one identity is the main Maxwell-theory reason the $E1$ and $T1$ channels can interfere in the same electric-parity radiation channel.

C.3. Rank-one light-shell loss and an exact finite-size anapole family

On the light shell $k^2 = \omega^2/c^2$, Eq. (81) depends only on

$$\boxed{\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega) := \mathbf{d}(\omega) + i\frac{\omega}{c^2}\mathbf{Q}(\omega)}. \quad (82)$$

Consequently the electric-parity $l = 1$ radiated power has the standard dipole-order form

$$\langle P_\infty^{(l=1)} \rangle(\omega) = \frac{\omega^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} |\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega)|^2, \quad (83)$$

up to regulator factors equal to one in the $kR \ll 1$ limit. The loss is rank one in the two-dimensional ($E1, T1$) source space: the light shell sees only \mathbf{d}_{eff} .

This also gives an explicit finite-size nonradiating family. Let a single vector coordinate $\mathbf{Q}(t)$ determine the polarization through

$$\mathbf{d}(t) = \frac{1}{c^2} \dot{\mathbf{Q}}(t), \quad \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{d}(t)\delta_R(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{J}_Q = \nabla \times \nabla \times (\mathbf{Q}\delta_R). \quad (84)$$

Then in Fourier space $\mathbf{d}(\omega) = -i\omega\mathbf{Q}(\omega)/c^2$. The bracket in Eq. (81) becomes

$$-i\omega\mathbf{d} + k^2\mathbf{Q} = \left(k^2 - \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}\right)\mathbf{Q}, \tag{85}$$

which vanishes on the light shell. Equivalently $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = \mathbf{0}$. The source is not zero; only its outgoing electric-parity $l = 1$ amplitude vanishes. This is the dynamic anapole cancellation used in the main text. If the slaving is perturbed by a smooth parameter, the zero is generically simple, so nearby frequencies are unprotected to first order.

C.4. PV part: local reactive oscillator block

The same field-eliminated functional supplies the conservative near-zone dynamics. Projecting Eq. (75) onto the localized basis above and retaining the PV part gives analytic low-frequency susceptibilities,

$$\chi_{EE}^{(PV)}(\omega; R) = K_e(R) - M_e(R)\omega^2 + O(\omega^4), \tag{86}$$

$$\chi_{QQ}^{(PV)}(\omega; R) = K_t(R) - M_t(R)\omega^2 + O(\omega^4), \tag{87}$$

$$\chi_{EQ}^{(PV)}(\omega; R) = i\Lambda_g(R)\omega + O(\omega^3). \tag{88}$$

The even entries become inertias and stiffnesses; the odd mixed entry becomes the one-derivative gyroscopic coupling. After absorbing regulator-sensitive pieces into the usual finite effective parameters, write

$$\mathbf{d} = \kappa_e\mathbf{q}_e, \quad \mathbf{Q} = \kappa_q\mathbf{q}_t. \tag{89}$$

The resulting local reactive Lagrangian is Eq. (90) below. The positivity of the renormalized inertias and stiffnesses is a stability assumption of the regulated mode, not a consequence of bare point-particle Maxwell theory.

Symbol map (internal appendix) To reduce notational overhead, we summarize the internal-sector symbols used below. All of these are *internal* parameters of the reduced $E1\oplus T1$ model (they are not the electron mass or charge unless stated explicitly).

Symbol	Meaning in this appendix
m_e, ω_e	inertia parameter and natural frequency of the E1 coordinate \mathbf{q}_e
m_t, ω_t	inertia parameter and natural frequency of the T1 coordinate \mathbf{q}_t
λ_g, g_λ	gyroscopic E1–T1 mixing; $g_\lambda = \lambda_g^2/(m_e m_t)$
κ_e	proportionality between \mathbf{q}_e and the electric dipole \mathbf{d}
κ_q	proportionality between \mathbf{q}_t and the toroidal source moment \mathbf{T}_{src}
κ_t	shorthand $\kappa_t := \kappa_q/c$ used in $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{d} + ik \mathbf{T}_{\text{eff}}$
\mathbf{q}_+, ω_0	bright eigenmode coordinate and its clock frequency $\omega_0 = \omega_+$
$\kappa_+(\omega)$	effective radiating dipole-order coefficient on the bright mode, defined by $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})} = \kappa_+ \mathbf{q}_+$
m_+	effective inertia of the bright mode
$\gamma_+(\omega), \Gamma_+(\omega)$	Rayleigh energy damping coefficient and corresponding spectral HWHM $\Gamma_+ = \gamma_+/2$

Two internal channels and one bright eigenmode At the retained multipole order the internal sector contains two vector degrees of freedom: an electric-parity $l = 1$ coordinate $\mathbf{q}_e(t)$ (E1) and a toroidal-parity partner $\mathbf{q}_t(t)$ (T1). The leading *reactive* local internal Lagrangian for this $E1 \oplus T1$ pair has the gyroscopic form

$$L_{\text{int}}^{(E1 \oplus T1)} = \frac{m_e}{2} (|\dot{\mathbf{q}}_e|^2 - \omega_e^2 |\mathbf{q}_e|^2) + \frac{m_t}{2} (|\dot{\mathbf{q}}_t|^2 - \omega_t^2 |\mathbf{q}_t|^2) + \frac{\lambda_g}{2} (\mathbf{q}_e \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}_t - \dot{\mathbf{q}}_e \cdot \mathbf{q}_t). \tag{90}$$

Varying \mathbf{q}_e and \mathbf{q}_t gives the coupled oscillator equations

$$m_e \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_e + m_e \omega_e^2 \mathbf{q}_e - \lambda_g \dot{\mathbf{q}}_t = \mathbf{0}, \quad m_t \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_t + m_t \omega_t^2 \mathbf{q}_t + \lambda_g \dot{\mathbf{q}}_e = \mathbf{0}. \tag{91}$$

For a monochromatic ansatz $\mathbf{q}_{e,t}(t) = \Re\{\mathbf{Q}_{e,t} e^{-i\omega t}\}$, the eigenfrequencies are

$$\omega_\pm^2 = \frac{\omega_e^2 + \omega_t^2 + g_\lambda}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(\omega_e^2 + \omega_t^2 + g_\lambda)^2 - 4\omega_e^2 \omega_t^2}, \quad g_\lambda := \frac{\lambda_g^2}{m_e m_t}. \tag{92}$$

We identify the fast *clock-line* frequency as $\omega_0 := \omega_+$. On an eigenmode, the two channels are locked in quadrature:

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = i \xi(\omega) \mathbf{Q}_e, \quad \xi(\omega) := \frac{m_e(\omega_e^2 - \omega^2)}{\omega \lambda_g}. \tag{93}$$

Dipole radiation sees only one bright combination At electric parity and $l = 1$, the far-field depends only on the *effective* dipole coefficient $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega)$, which is a fixed linear combination of the E1 and T1 source amplitudes. In the notation of Subsection 2.2,

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega) = \kappa_e \mathbf{q}_e(\omega) + ik(\omega) \kappa_t \mathbf{q}_t(\omega), \quad k(\omega) = \frac{\omega}{c}, \quad \kappa_t := \frac{1}{c} \kappa_q. \tag{94}$$

On the clock eigenmode at $\omega = \omega_0$, inserting Eq. (93) gives

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \left[\kappa_e - \frac{\omega_0}{c^2} \kappa_q \xi(\omega_0) \right] \mathbf{Q}_e(\omega_0).$$

Thus the clock line is *protected* (dynamic anapole) if and only if

$$\boxed{\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0} \iff \kappa_e = k(\omega_0) \kappa_t \xi(\omega_0).} \tag{95}$$

C.5. Worked Maxwell-theory example: an explicit anapole root in a finite-size source

Because the protected clock mode is the most model-specific physical ingredient in the clock interface, it is helpful to record one explicit Maxwell-theory example in which the coefficient $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega)$ has a simple interference zero while the internal fields remain nonzero. At retained electric-parity $l = 1$ order, the far field depends only on the combination $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{d} + ik \mathbf{T}_{\text{eff}}$ (Eq. (10)), so the dipole-order radiated power is proportional to $|\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega)|^2$. In the idealized point-source limit, the exact radiated fields of a co-located electric dipole and toroidal dipole are proportional to the same combination (up to a sign convention), and therefore vanish identically in the radiation zone when $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}$ [19,21].

A concrete finite-size realization can be sketched analytically by combining a subwavelength toroidal solenoid (major radius R , minor radius a) carrying a poloidal current $I e^{-i\omega t}$ with a short capacitive gap of length ℓ on the same driven mode. For a thin torus, the poloidal current produces a toroidal source moment of order

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{src}}(\omega) \approx \frac{\pi}{2} N I a^2 R \hat{\mathbf{z}} \quad (\text{units } \text{A}\cdot\text{m}^3),$$

where N is the number of turns. By charge continuity, the same current produces a gap charge amplitude $Q = I/(i\omega)$, hence an ordinary electric dipole moment

$$\mathbf{d}(\omega) \approx Q \ell \hat{\mathbf{z}} = \frac{I \ell}{i\omega} \hat{\mathbf{z}}.$$

Substituting these estimates into Eq. (10) gives

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}(\omega) \approx iI \left[-\frac{\ell}{\omega} + \frac{\omega}{c^2} \frac{\pi}{2} N a^2 R \right] \hat{\mathbf{z}},$$

so the dipole-order radiation cancels at the real frequency

$$\omega_0^2 \approx \frac{2c^2 \ell}{\pi N a^2 R}. \tag{96}$$

Eq. (96) is included solely as a proof-of-principle: standard Maxwell theory admits localized sources whose dipole-order radiation coefficient has a simple interference zero (a dynamic anapole) while the internal near-zone fields remain finite, and such zeros can occur on high- Q resonant modes. The regulated clock interface above realizes the same

structure internally: the fast bright mode is the phase-locked $E1 \oplus T1$ mode on which $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) = \mathbf{0}$.

This cancellation is automatically *frequency-local*: unless parameters are tuned to make the bracketed factor a double zero, $\partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}|_{\omega_0} \neq \mathbf{0}$. In any finite-size implementation, higher multipoles (M1, E2, ...) remain and set a finite clock linewidth; in the usual subwavelength regime $k_0 R \ll 1$ their power is suppressed by $O((k_0 R)^2)$ relative to an unprotected E1 channel at the same frequency. Experimentally and numerically, such anapole roots appear as pronounced scattering dips and can support very high- Q resonances in subwavelength metamaterial or dielectric structures [18–21].

Slope at the root and frequency-local protection. Along the clock eigenmode one may write

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega) = \left[\kappa_e - \frac{\omega}{c^2} \kappa_q \xi(\omega) \right] \mathbf{Q}_e(\omega),$$

so (treating the eigenmode amplitude $\mathbf{Q}_e(\omega)$ as slowly varying across the narrow protection window) the *local* slope at the interference root is controlled by the bracket:

$$\partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})} \Big|_{\omega_0} \simeq \left[-\frac{\kappa_q}{c^2} \xi(\omega_0) - \frac{\omega_0}{c^2} \kappa_q \xi'(\omega_0) \right] \mathbf{Q}_e(\omega_0). \tag{97}$$

Using the sealing condition in Eq. (95), the first term becomes $-(\kappa_e/\omega_0)\mathbf{Q}_e(\omega_0)$. Unless a further tuning enforces $\xi'(\omega_0) \approx -\xi(\omega_0)/\omega_0$ (a “double root”), the second term is of the same order. Thus, generically,

$$\left| \partial_\omega \mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega_0) \right| = O\left(\frac{|d_0|}{\omega_0} \right), \tag{98}$$

which is the quantitative content of *frequency-local* protection used in the leakage argument of Appendix A.

Why this produces a single clock oscillator. After diagonalizing the reactive $E1 \oplus T1$ block, one may define the *bright* clock coordinate $\mathbf{q}_+(t)$ as the fast eigenmode at ω_0 . Dipole-order radiation damping attaches to this one bright coordinate (rank–1 in the $E1 \oplus T1$ space), while the orthogonal combination is dark at that order. On the protected clock state, the bright mode remains a well-defined narrowband oscillator with an action–angle pair (J_+, ϕ) , which is the only internal degree of freedom retained in the phase-closure derivation. In the covariant worldline description of Section 3, the internal Hamiltonian is approximately $H_{\text{int}} \simeq \omega_0 J_+$ on this mode, so the canonical equation gives $d\phi/d\tau = \partial H_{\text{int}}/\partial J_+ \simeq \omega_0$ and therefore $\dot{\phi} = \omega_0 d\tau/dt$.

Frequency-locality is generic: $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega)$ is smooth in ω and the condition in Eq. (95) is a simple root unless additional tuning creates a double root, so detuned lines $\omega_0 + \Delta$ are not protected to leading order.

This is the concrete sense in which the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction supplies (i) a *localized* fast clock line at ω_0 and (ii) a *frequency-local* protection condition for that clock line, while leaving other radiative channels (M1, higher multipoles, orbital-band emission) as separate questions.

Dipole-order Rayleigh loss and a linewidth estimate. At dipole order, the far-zone electric-parity $l = 1$ power depends only on $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega)$. In a narrowband bright-mode description one may write $\mathbf{d}_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{int})}(\omega) = \kappa_+(\omega) \mathbf{q}_+(\omega)$, where \mathbf{q}_+ is the bright clock coordinate. For a harmonic component at frequency ω this gives the usual dipole power

$$\langle P_{E1} \rangle = \frac{\omega^4}{12\pi\epsilon_0 c^3} |\kappa_+(\omega)|^2 |\mathbf{q}_+(\omega)|^2.$$

The same loss can be represented by a local Rayleigh functional $\mathcal{R}_+ = \frac{m_+}{2} \gamma_+ |\dot{\mathbf{q}}_+|^2$. Matching the cycle-averaged power yields the standard (energy) damping coefficient

$$\gamma_+(\omega) = \tau_+(\omega) \omega^2, \quad \tau_+(\omega) = \frac{|\kappa_+(\omega)|^2}{6\pi\epsilon_0 m_+ c^3}. \tag{99}$$

In a Gaussian-regulated near-zone estimate, the renormalized inertias m_e, m_t (and hence m_+) are of the near-field scale $m \sim \kappa_{\text{typ}}^2 / (\epsilon_0 c^2 R)$, where κ_{typ} denotes a *typical uncanceled* internal conversion scale (for example $\kappa_{\text{typ}} \sim \kappa_e$ or κ_q), not the canceled radiative coefficient $\kappa_+(\omega_0)$ at the protected line. Thus away from the interference root one expects $\tau_+ = O(R/c)$.

With the linewidth convention of the main text, the corresponding dipole spectral half-width is $\Gamma_+(\omega) = \gamma_+(\omega)/2$. On the protected clock state $\kappa_+(\omega_0) = 0$, hence $\Gamma_+(\omega_0) = 0$ at dipole order; the residual clock linewidth Γ_0 is then set by the next radiating channels and is suppressed by $O((k_0 R)^2)$ in the small-source regime, leading to the parametric estimate

$$\Gamma_0 = O(\omega_0 (k_0 R)^3), \quad Q_0 := \frac{\omega_0}{\Gamma_0} = O((k_0 R)^{-3}), \quad k_0 := \frac{\omega_0}{c}, \tag{100}$$

in the small-source regime.

A full Maxwell-theory construction of a nonradiating accelerated *point* charge does not exist; sealing here refers instead to an *extended, internally structured* dressed source, and only within a controlled multipole/near-zone truncation.

D. Sealing premise supplements: frequency-locality and a consistent window

This appendix collects two short supplements that are conceptually useful but not needed for the EBK derivation. First, we show in a two-channel toy model why an interference-type protection root is generically *frequency-local*. Second, we record one

order-of-magnitude window showing that the hierarchy assumptions invoked for the selection argument can be mutually compatible.

D.1. A two-channel toy model for frequency-local protection Fix one outgoing

electric-parity $l = 1$ channel and project onto it so that the effective dipole coefficient becomes a complex scalar $d_{\text{eff}}(\omega)$. Suppose the two dipole-order source channels factor through a single narrowband mode amplitude $a(\omega)$ as

$$d(\omega) = d_+ a(\omega), \quad T_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = T_+ a(\omega),$$

with complex constants d_+, T_+ fixed by the internal mode shape. Then Eq. (10) becomes

$$d_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = [d_+ + ik(\omega) T_+] a(\omega).$$

A protected line at ω_0 can occur either because the bracketed factor vanishes (an *interference* root) with $a(\omega_0) \neq 0$, or because $a(\omega_0) = 0$. For the interference case, differentiation gives

$$\partial_\omega d_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = \frac{i}{c} T_+ a(\omega) + [d_+ + ik(\omega) T_+] a'(\omega).$$

At the interference root the second term vanishes at ω_0 , so $\partial_\omega d_{\text{eff}}(\omega_0) = iT_+ a(\omega_0)/c \neq 0$ whenever the second channel is present. Thus the protection is simple and therefore frequency-local: $d_{\text{eff}}(\omega_0 + \Delta) = O(\Delta)$ and the dipole power is $O(\Delta^2)$.

D.2. A scale hierarchy window The selection argument concerns the near-line sidebands

produced by slow quasi-periodic modulation on a Kepler torus. It is cleanest when: (i) the clock line at ω_0 is narrowband ($\Gamma_0 \ll \omega_0$), (ii) the near-line comb is resolved ($\Gamma_0 \lesssim \Omega$), and (iii) the sideband detunings (scale Ω) lie inside the locality window ($\Omega \ll \Delta_{\text{loc}}$ with Δ_{loc} from Eq. (11)). In the small-source regime $k_0 R \ll 1$ one expects Γ_0 to be suppressed by higher-multipole factors; Eq. (100) gives one parametric estimate within the retained $E1 \oplus T1$ truncation.

D.3. One numerical window (optional) As a simple order-of-magnitude check, adopt the

external calibration $J_{\tau 0} = \hbar$ (only to set scales), so that $\omega_0 = 2\mu c^2/\hbar$. Choosing a localized internal scale $R \sim r_e$ (the classical electron radius, used here only as a convenient small length) gives $k_0 R \sim 1.5 \times 10^{-2} \ll 1$. Eq. (100) then suggests a radiatively limited $Q_0 \sim (k_0 R)^{-3} \sim 3 \times 10^5$ and hence $\Gamma_0 \sim \omega_0/Q_0$. At Bohr scales one has $\Omega/\omega_0 \sim 10^{-5}$, so $\Gamma_0 \lesssim \Omega$ and $\Omega \ll \Delta_{\text{loc}}$ can hold simultaneously in at least one nonempty window. These numbers are not claimed as a model of the real electron; they only illustrate that the scale inequalities assumed for the mechanism are not mutually contradictory.

E. Why the averaged slow Lagrangian has the $J_+ \mathcal{A}(\dot{\gamma})$ structure

The main text uses a structural input: after averaging over a fast clock phase, the remaining slow dynamics has a first-order Lagrangian in which the clock action J_+ couples linearly to the slow rates through a 1-form \mathcal{A} on the slow torus. Here we give the minimal canonical reason why such a term is natural, and we record (briefly) how it is realized in the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction.

E.1. Slow-dependent rephasing produces a 1-form coupling

Assume the slow subsystem is integrable and admits action–angle variables (J_i, ϑ^i) , and assume the internal clock line is narrowband with an action–phase pair (J_+, ϕ) and Hamiltonian $H_{\text{int}}(J_+)$. Before any coupling, the first-order Lagrangian is

$$L_0 = \sum_i J_i \dot{\vartheta}^i + J_+ \dot{\phi} - H_{\text{slow}}(J) - H_{\text{int}}(J_+).$$

Because ϕ is an angle, its zero is a convention. In particular one may choose a *slow-dependent* phase convention $\phi = \phi' + \chi(\vartheta)$ with χ single-valued on the slow torus. Then

$$J_+ \dot{\phi} = J_+ \dot{\phi}' + J_+ \partial_i \chi \dot{\vartheta}^i,$$

so a slow-dependent rephasing generates a term linear in the slow rates and proportional to J_+ . Equivalently, it produces $J_+ \mathcal{A}(\dot{\gamma})$ with $\mathcal{A} = \partial_i \chi \, d\vartheta^i$.

More generally, after slow–fast averaging, any surviving coupling term that is (i) linear in the slow rates and (ii) proportional to J_+ can be written as J_+ times a 1-form \mathcal{A} on the slow manifold. The freedom $\phi \mapsto \phi + \chi(\vartheta)$ corresponds to the gauge shift $\mathcal{A} \mapsto \mathcal{A} - d\chi$; the gauge-invariant content is carried by loop integrals $\oint \mathcal{A}$.

Specializing $(\vartheta^1, \vartheta^2) = (\theta, \alpha_r)$ gives the structure written in Eqs. (13)–(18).

E.2. Regulated Maxwell–Lorentz realization (brief)

The main text separates the geometric phase-closure step from the clock-interface step. In the present regulated-source formulation the localized clock line and its protected long-lived regime are supplied by an explicit Maxwell–Lorentz near-zone reduction for a dressed charge, once the finite source and localized internal current sector are admitted as regulated-source inputs. In outline: the reduced internal sector contains a radiating “bright” oscillation together with a partner mode. The effective dipole moment is a linear combination of the two; at a tuned clock frequency ω_0 their contributions cancel, so the net clock-line dipole seen in the far field vanishes (protection). In that protected regime the bright coordinate is narrowband and admits the action–angle description (J_+, ϕ) used here.

The present paper includes the clock-interface ingredients needed for the phase-closure argument in Appendix C and then isolates the geometric consequence of the proper-time phase law.

F. Estimates for subleading contributions to the drift 1-form

The main text isolates the universal proper-time contribution \mathcal{A}_τ to the phase-drift 1-form. In any concrete Maxwell–Lorentz reduction there can be additional averaged couplings, summarized by $\delta\mathcal{A}$ in Eq. (34). For phase closure, the only data that matter are the *generator periods* $\oint_{\gamma_i} \delta\mathcal{A}$. This appendix records a few representative sources of $\delta\mathcal{A}$ and their parametric size in the regime assumed throughout: nonrelativistic motion $v/c \ll 1$, adiabatic separation $\Omega/\omega_0 \ll 1$, and a near-zone/multipole hierarchy $k_0R \ll 1$.

F.1. Representative sources and suppressions

In the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction, $\delta\mathcal{A}$ is generated by subleading worldline and near-zone operators (magnetostatic/Darwin-type terms, finite-size corrections, and adiabatic corrections to the stable internal eigenmode). Appendix C records the retained source hierarchy, and standard effective-field-theory power counting for radiative systems gives the same symmetry-based suppression pattern [27]. A schematic summary is:

Representative source of $\delta\mathcal{A}$	Typical suppression of $\oint \delta\mathcal{A}$
Next proper-time term in $d\tau/dt$ (v^4/c^4)	$\sim v^2/c^2$
Adiabatic corrections (slow dependence of an internal eigenvector)	$\sim \Omega/\Delta_{\text{int}}$
Finite-size/multipole operators (source size R)	$\sim (k_0R)^2$
Velocity-dependent EM dressing (Darwin/magnetostatic, ...)	higher order in v/c

The entries in this table are not independent “new assumptions”: they are the same small parameters already used to justify (i) the proper-time expansion, (ii) the slow–fast averaging, and (iii) the near-zone/multipole truncation.

F.2. Example: Darwin/magnetostatic correction to the momentum identity

The conversion $v^2 dt \mapsto (\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r})/\mu$ used in deriving \mathcal{A}_τ (Subsection 4.1) is exact in the electrostatic Kepler truncation where $\mathbf{p} = \mu\mathbf{v}$. In a Maxwell–Lorentz reduction at the next order, eliminating the field produces velocity-dependent interactions (Darwin/magnetostatic terms), so the canonical momentum has the schematic form

$$\mathbf{p} = \mu\mathbf{v} + \delta\mathbf{p}, \quad \delta\mathbf{p} = O\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)\mu\mathbf{v}, \tag{101}$$

(for example, the Darwin Lagrangian produces terms $\delta\mathbf{p} \propto (\kappa_C/(c^2r))\mathbf{v}$ and $\delta\mathbf{p} \propto (v^2/c^2)\mathbf{v}$; see e.g. [12,13]). Then

$$\mu v^2 dt = \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r} - \delta\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r},$$

so the lab-time envelope construction produces, in addition to \mathcal{A}_τ , a correction 1-form

$$\delta\mathcal{A}_D = \frac{\omega_0}{2\mu c^2} \delta\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r}. \tag{102}$$

Its generator periods satisfy the bound

$$\left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \delta\mathcal{A}_D \right| \lesssim O\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}_\tau \right| = O\left(\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) 2\pi \frac{J_i}{J_{\tau 0}}, \quad i \in \{\theta, r\}. \tag{103}$$

On the Coulomb EBK lattice $J_i = O(nJ_{\tau 0})$ and the orbital speed scales as $v/c \sim \kappa_C/(cJ_{\text{Kep}}) \sim \alpha_\tau/n$, so $|\oint \delta\mathcal{A}_D| = O(2\pi \alpha_\tau^2/n) \ll 1$ for low n . In words: Darwin/magnetostatic dressing shifts the generator phase returns, but only at fine-structure order in the same parameter that controls the nonrelativistic regime.

F.3. Example: the next proper-time term

Keeping the next term in $\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = 1 - \frac{v^2}{2c^2} - \frac{v^4}{8c^4} + O(v^6/c^6)$ adds

$$d\tilde{\phi}_{\tau,4} = -\frac{\omega_0}{8c^4} v^4 dt.$$

Using $v^2 dt = (\mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{r})/\mu$ gives a correction 1-form of the schematic size

$$\delta\mathcal{A}_{\tau,4} \sim \frac{v^2}{4c^2} \mathcal{A}_\tau \implies \left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \delta\mathcal{A}_{\tau,4} \right| \lesssim \frac{\langle v^2 \rangle}{4c^2} \left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \mathcal{A}_\tau \right|.$$

On Coulomb orbits one has $v/c \sim \kappa_C/(cJ_{\text{Kep}})$, so under $J_{\text{Kep}} \sim nJ_{\tau 0}$ this gives a generator-period suppression $|\oint \delta\mathcal{A}_{\tau,4}|/2\pi = O(n^{-2})$ in the same small parameter that controls the nonrelativistic regime.

F.4. Example: adiabatic mode projection

A second standard source of $\delta\mathcal{A}$ (and one that appears naturally in the regulated internal reduction) is *adiabatic projection onto a slowly varying bright eigenmode*. The retained regulated $E1 \oplus T1$ sector is a small vector of oscillator coordinates. After diagonalization, one projects that vector onto the bright eigenvector to obtain the scalar bright coordinate $q_+(t)$ (Appendix C). If the bright eigenvector $\mathbf{u}_+(I)$ depends weakly on the slow orbital invariants $I = (J_r, J_\theta)$, one may write the complex clock envelope schematically as

$$\mathbf{Q}(t) = a(t) \mathbf{u}_+(I(t)), \quad \dot{I} = O(\Omega),$$

where $a(t)$ is the scalar complex amplitude. Substituting this into the canonical one-form of the fast sector produces, in addition to $J_+ \dot{\phi}$, a geometric term

$$J_+ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_+^\dagger \dot{\mathbf{u}}_+) = J_+ \delta \mathcal{A}_{\text{ad}}(\dot{\gamma}), \quad \delta \mathcal{A}_{\text{ad}} := \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_+^\dagger d\mathbf{u}_+),$$

which is a contribution to the drift 1-form. Because \mathbf{u}_+ is an instantaneous eigenvector, nondegenerate perturbation theory gives

$$\|\partial_I \mathbf{u}_+\| = O\left(\frac{\|\partial_I H_{\text{int}}\|}{\Delta_{\text{int}}}\right),$$

where Δ_{int} is the separation to the nearest internal mode. Hence along any generator cycle,

$$\left| \oint_{\gamma_i} \delta \mathcal{A}_{\text{ad}} \right| = O\left(\frac{\Omega}{\Delta_{\text{int}}}\right) \ll 1 \quad (i \in \{\theta, r\}), \tag{104}$$

provided $\Omega \ll \Delta_{\text{int}}$, which is already part of the protection locality hierarchy (Eq. (11)).

F.5. When proper-time dominance can fail

The “one-scale” lattice in units of $J_{\tau 0}$ is therefore a prediction of a *regime* rather than an identity. It can fail if the reduction produces a contribution with order-one generator periods. Concrete failure modes include:

- internal near-degeneracy or strong mode mixing so that $\Delta_{\text{int}} \sim \Omega$ and the adiabatic projection term gives $\oint \delta \mathcal{A}_{\text{ad}} = O(1)$,
- breakdown of the near-zone hierarchy $k_0 R \ll 1$ so that higher multipoles are not suppressed and clock-line-scale corrections are no longer perturbative,
- velocity-dependent dressing that is not suppressed by v^2/c^2 (so that $\delta \mathbf{p}$ becomes comparable to μv on a generator cycle),
- nonlocal memory terms (from field elimination or radiation reaction) that destroy the description of the drift as a closed 1-form on a torus.

In such regimes the EBK lattice need not emerge, and the present mechanism simply does not apply.

G. Defect slips: fold caustics and the Coulomb origin

Section 6 uses the Coulomb defect pair in Eq. (47). This appendix records the standard local normal forms that yield $\nu_r = 2$ (turning points) and $\nu_\theta = 2$ (the Coulomb origin) when one continues an oscillatory return object through the corresponding singularities. The discussion is stationary-phase mathematics and does not rely on a wavefunction interpretation [3,4].

G.1. Turning points, fold caustics, and the radial Maslov index

A wide class of return quantities built from a rapidly varying phase reduces locally to an oscillatory integral of the form

$$I(\lambda) = \int W(s; \lambda) \exp\left(i\Phi(s; \lambda)/J_{\tau_0}\right) ds, \quad (105)$$

where s is a local coordinate, W varies slowly, and Φ/J_{τ_0} is a large phase. A radial turning point is precisely where the stationary-phase structure changes: in local coordinates one meets a fold where

$$\partial_s \Phi = 0, \quad \partial_s^2 \Phi = 0, \quad \partial_s^3 \Phi \neq 0.$$

Expanding Φ about the fold and rescaling s brings Eq. (105) to the Airy normal form

$$I(\lambda) \propto \int \exp\left(i(\zeta u + u^3/3)\right) du = 2\pi \text{Ai}(\zeta), \quad (106)$$

where ζ is the unfolded control parameter (its sign distinguishes the oscillatory and evanescent sides).

The universal phase offset appears in the oscillatory asymptotics: for large positive ζ ,

$$\text{Ai}(-\zeta) \sim \zeta^{-1/4} \sin\left(\frac{2}{3}\zeta^{3/2} + \frac{\pi}{4}\right).$$

Thus continuing the oscillatory object through one turning point produces a fixed phase slip of $+\pi/2$ relative to a naive “two-mode” stationary-phase continuation. A bound Kepler ellipse has two radial turning points per radial cycle (pericenter and apocenter), hence the radial defect index is $\nu_r = 2$ as stated in Eq. (45).

G.2. Coulomb origin, Cartesian regularity, and the Langer half-shift

The Coulomb problem also has a singular point of a different kind: the polar coordinate singularity at $r = 0$. Although the *slow orbit* in this paper is planar, regularity of the return amplitude at the Coulomb center is inherited from the underlying three-dimensional central-force problem: the relevant envelope must be smooth in Cartesian coordinates at $r = 0$ before restricting to an orbital plane.²

In the phase-closure mechanism the relevant return object is the defect-corrected clock factor U , obtained by transporting the internal clock and projecting back onto the same internal mode. The only structural input needed for the Langer half-shift is that, near $r = 0$,

² If one truly posed a two-dimensional field theory and imposed regularity in two-dimensional polar coordinates, the centrifugal structure would differ. The hydrogenic principal offset $n = n_r + \ell + 1$ is therefore a diagnostic of three-dimensional origin regularity.

this return amplitude admits a *local*, rotationally invariant *second-order* scalar normal form with smooth coefficients (a standard Liouville/Sturm–Liouville setting). In the regulated Maxwell–Lorentz reduction this normal form arises at retained dipole order after mode projection, as summarized in Appendix C.

A convenient way to package the universal step is the following lemma.

Lemma 2 (Langer half-shift from a local second-order Cartesian-regular normal form).

Let $W(\mathbf{r})$ be a complex return amplitude. Assume that, in a neighborhood of $r = 0$:

1. W is regular in Cartesian coordinates at $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}$;
2. W obeys a linear *second-order* local equation with smooth coefficients;
3. that local equation is rotationally invariant (depends on \mathbf{r} only through $r = |\mathbf{r}|$).

Then separation into spherical harmonics yields the universal centrifugal singularity $\ell(\ell + 1)/r^2$ in the radial normal form, and passing to a regular radial coordinate forces the replacement $\ell(\ell + 1) \mapsto (\ell + \frac{1}{2})^2$. Equivalently, the angular defect index is $\nu_\theta = 2$.

Proof. A representative local rotationally invariant second-order normal form can be written schematically as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}}W = 0, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}} = \Delta + f(r), \tag{107}$$

with $f(r)$ smooth near $r = 0$. Writing $W(\mathbf{r}) = R(r) Y_{\ell m}(\hat{\mathbf{r}})$ and using

$$\Delta W = \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \partial_r (r^2 \partial_r R) - \frac{\ell(\ell + 1)}{r^2} R \right) Y_{\ell m},$$

one finds the universal centrifugal coefficient $\ell(\ell + 1)/r^2$ in the separated radial equation.

After the standard substitution $u = rR$, the radial equation takes the Liouville form

$$u''(r) + \left[k^2(r) - \frac{\ell(\ell + 1)}{r^2} \right] u(r) = 0, \tag{108}$$

where $k^2(r)$ collects the smooth (nonsingular) terms, including the Coulomb potential. On $r > 0$ set $r = e^x$ and write $u(r) = e^{x/2} y(x)$. Using $u_r = e^{-x} u_x$ and $u_{rr} = e^{-2x}(u_{xx} - u_x)$, Eq. (108) becomes

$$y''(x) + \left[e^{2x} k^2(e^x) - \left(\ell + \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right] y(x) = 0. \tag{109}$$

Thus the regular radial coordinate forces the replacement

$$\ell(\ell + 1) \mapsto \ell(\ell + 1) + \frac{1}{4} = \left(\ell + \frac{1}{2} \right)^2,$$

which is the Langer half-shift. In the generator-period language this corresponds to a fixed $+\pi$ defect on the angular cycle, i.e. $\nu_\theta = 2$ as stated in Eq. (46). □

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